

Nonlinear SSC Modelling of Blazars

Master's Thesis
University of Turku
Dept. of Physics and Astronomy
Astronomy
2014
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Master's Thesis, 104 pages
Astronomy
March 2014

Blazars are powerful extragalactic sources that emit bulk of radiation close to line of sight and the origin of their radiation is believed to be non-thermal. Various models have been used over the years, including many non-thermal radiation components, to account for their observed spectra. Generally, Synchrotron Self-Compton (SSC) models have been successfully used in many blazars mainly including high synchrotron peak BL Lacs (HBLs). In case of Flat Spectrum Radio Quasars (FSRQs), pure SSC models generally have been failed to match higher luminosity of gamma-rays while External Compton (EC) modelling conveniently explains the high energy part of their Spectral Energy Distribution (SED), especially gamma-rays.

In this thesis, I report the implications of a time dependent nonlinear SSC model in blazar SED modelling. I argue that in many flaring sources, linear SSC cooling relation should be replaced by nonlinear cooling term in order to meet high gamma ray fluxes in Compton dominated sources. FSRQs show higher Compton domination than BL Lacs, and most of the modelling schemes employ EC cooling to model their high gamma ray fluxes. The nonlinear SSC modelling suffice these sources. In less dominated sources in selected blazar sample, mainly including LBLs, the one-zone model cannot account for source SED and a multi-component SSC model is used to explain the SEDs. In case of HBLs, the source SEDs can be successfully modelled with one-zone nonlinear SSC model and results are consistently in agreement with historical modelling of these sources. However the model predicts much steeper TeV spectra in HBLs, which is not always observed.

I have modelled the published simultaneous multifrequency data for gamma-ray loud AGNs with the nonlinear SSC model and found better SSC fits than many other models that rely on steady state linear SSC cooling mechanism. The nonlinear SSC cooling term depends on integral of electron distribution itself, suggesting that a higher injection of electrons in compact source would lead to higher SSC luminosity. While a one-zone and multizone SSC model, assuming a mono-energetic electrons injection in the active zone, efficiently meet the observations in all blazars presented, power law or multiple power law electron spectra may produce better SED fits. Generally, the high gamma-ray luminosity is attributed to contribution of external photons to inverse Compton scattering, however, the nonlinear model explains the very high gamma-ray fluxes of flaring source in terms of higher particle injection into radiative zone. This suggests that the nonthermal flares may be triggered by a higher injection of electrons into jet and not necessarily due to increased external radiation field. I argue that nonlinear SSC model might be successfully used in explaining extreme gamma-ray flares that lead to observed higher Compton domination in some blazars.

Contents

1	Active Galactic Nuclei	1
1.1	Introduction to Active Galactic Nuclei	1
1.2	Characteristics and Features	2
1.2.1	High Luminosity and Point like Appearance	2
1.2.2	Spectral Line Emission	3
1.2.3	High Flux Variability	3
1.2.4	Nonthermal Emission	4
1.2.5	Broadband Spectra	4
1.3	AGN Paradigm	5
1.4	Standard Model of AGN	7
2	Blazar Phenomenon	10
2.1	Radiation Mechanisms in Blazars	12
2.1.1	Synchrotron Radiation	12
2.1.2	Inverse Compton Radiation	14
2.2	Spectral Energy Distribution	17
3	Blazar SSC Modelling	21
3.1	Non-linear SSC Model	23
3.1.1	Injection Parameter	25
3.2	Data	27
4	Blazar SED modelling	30
4.1	3C 454.3	31
4.1.1	2009 SED Modelling	31
4.1.2	2008 SED Modelling	37
4.1.3	2010 Flare SED Modelling	40

4.1.4	Discussion	42
4.2	3C 279	44
4.2.1	2010 SED Modelling	44
4.2.2	2008 SED Modelling	48
4.2.3	Discussion	50
4.3	FSRQ Sample	55
4.4	BL Lacertae	61
4.5	PKS 2155-304	67
4.6	Mrk 501	71
4.6.1	SED Modelling	71
4.6.2	Discussion	75
4.7	Mrk 421	77
4.7.1	SED Modelling	77
4.7.2	Discussion	81
4.8	BL Lac Sample	83
4.9	Parameter Correlation	89
4.9.1	α vs γ_0	89
4.9.2	B vs γ_0	91
4.9.3	γ_0 vs ν_s	92
5	Results and Discussion	93
5.1	FSRQs and LBLs	94
5.2	HBLs	97
5.3	Summary and Conclusion	99
	References	100

1 Active Galactic Nuclei

1.1 Introduction to Active Galactic Nuclei

In our universe most of galaxies behave normally, meaning that their radiation is due to sum of the emission from stars, interstellar medium and dust. The galaxies in our universe are believed to host a black hole in their center, however the intensity of black hole activity is not same in each of them. Roughly 10% of all galaxies are considered to be active. An active galaxy holds a Supermassive Black hole (SMBH) with typical mass of $10^8 M_{\odot}$, which violently accretes the surrounding gas and dust from stars and interstellar medium.

Active Galactic Nuclei (AGNs) are the among the most exotic objects on the extragalactic sky. They represent the central bright compact regions of active galaxies and outshine the background starlight from entire galaxy. AGNs have high luminosity (as high as 10^{48} erg s^{-1}) and often appear as point like sources on the sky. After the discovery of radio telescopes, AGNs were observed extensively in the radio band and then, later on, their gamma-ray counterparts were discovered. These multiwavelength emitters optically seem to have point like "*quasi-stellar*" appearance.

The radiation in active galaxies is believed to be produced by accretion of matter on the compact massive black holes. The gas in the vicinity of black hole is trapped in its gravitational potential and loses angular momentum due to turbulent fluid flow in the disk. The change in angular momentum of gas is compensated in form of a jet of matter emitted from black hole. The radiation from AGNs is of both thermal and the nonthermal origin but nonthermal radiation is a hallmark of AGNs, as the very high luminosity from a compact region cannot be produced by nuclear fusion reactions. AGNs appear to be highly variable sources at all wavelengths. AGNs are a major class of objects on sky that emit at radio, X-rays and gamma-rays and (in

some cases) TeV gamma-rays. The accretion luminosity L is given by:

$$L = \eta \dot{M} c^2 \quad (1)$$

Here η is the efficiency of the process, \dot{M} is the rate of infalling mass and c is velocity of light. The hydrostatic balance between the outward radiation pressure and inward gravitational force gives an upper limit to observed luminosity referred as *Eddington luminosity* as given by:

$$L_E = 4\pi G M_b m_p c / \sigma_T \quad (2)$$

Where G is gravitational constant, M_b is mass of black hole, m_p is mass of a proton and σ_T is Thomson scattering cross-section.

One of main motivation for AGN studies is their broadband emission across the whole electromagnetic spectrum extending from radio to VHE gamma-rays. They can be used as laboratories to study the extreme accelerations and interactions of radiation and matter, involving hot relativistic plasma under the influence of electromagnetic field and intense gravity. This makes them interesting and special objects to study at all wavelengths.

1.2 Characteristics and Features

There is no real and physical definition for AGNs as all of these sources do not always exhibit the same set of properties. The best way to define them is to investigate their common characteristics and features.

1.2.1 High Luminosity and Point like Appearance

AGNs appear to be highly luminous and compact point sources. The first observational identifier of AGNs is their optical point like appearance that still goes unresolved up-to-date. The name *quasar* was coined due to quasi stellar appearance of the nuclei. The AGNs appear as point sources as the emission from the central core

swamps the emission from the host galaxy. The point likeness of an AGN depends on the ratio of nucleus to host galaxy luminosity, redshift and observed wavelength. The optical emission is not necessarily always from the core and may arise in the host galaxy or circum-nuclear gas and matter. AGNs are highly luminous with an average host galaxy luminosity of about 10^{44} erg s⁻¹. There are, however, faint nuclei, where it is not possible to distinguish them against background starlight from their host galaxies due to obscuration by dust along the line of sight or low signal-to-noise ratio.

1.2.2 Spectral Line Emission

AGNs also show peculiar line spectra at optical and ultraviolet (UV) wavelengths. The fast moving gas clouds produce line emission under the gravitational influence of black hole. The emitted lines are classified as 'broad' or 'narrow' depending on line width. In some AGNs, the emission lines are broad and spread over a substantial range of frequencies with related dispersion velocities in few thousands of km s⁻¹. These broad lines are produced due to Doppler shift of orbiting gas. Typical frequently observed lines are $H\alpha$, $Fe[II]$, $C[IV]$ doublet, etc. Narrow emission lines are practically present in all sources. Broad line emission is not present in all AGNs [1], hence its strength is also taken under consideration while building the classification schemes. The spectral lines are used in AGNs to calculate their redshift. The redshift is mainly of cosmological origin and highest known value for quasars is 7 [2].

1.2.3 High Flux Variability

AGNs are highly variable sources at in all bands from radio [3] to gamma-rays [5]. Both the short-term and long-term variability is reported in AGNs. The flux variability is observed in all bands and the variability timescales varying from years

to hours or minutes [4]. The timescales get shorter when AGNs are probed at higher energies, for example at TeV energies, the variations are observed on timescale of minutes [6]. For a good review on variability in AGNs, in particular radio quiet AGNs, see [7]. AGNs, sometimes, show multifrequency flux correlation [8] which connects the radio emission to high energies. Such correlation helps to understand emission processes and constraining physical models.

1.2.4 Nonthermal Emission

The spectrum of the galaxies can be described by superposition of stellar thermal (black body) spectra. Since temperature of stars varies within a narrow range from few thousands to few tens of thousand K, the observed broad band energy distribution of AGNs cannot be explained by thermal radiation processes. The emission of AGN at different wavelengths may arise due to different phenomena, however, these sources are believed to be the dominant emitters of nonthermal origin in extragalactic universe. The emission is mainly assumed to arise from synchrotron and inverse Compton processes which are discussed in Section 2.1. However, the entire emission from AGNs is not always of nonthermal origin. The observed optical and UV flux of the these sources is generally believed to be significantly dominated by star light with fractional contribution from surrounding gas and dust.

1.2.5 Broadband Spectra

AGNs emit over the entire electromagnetic spectral range from radio to gamma-rays and even TeV rays. This is peculiar to AGNs only while the normal stars and galaxies do not radiate through the entire electromagnetic spectrum. Emission at optical-UV and soft X-rays is practically present in all galaxies, however only $\sim 15\%$ of AGNs are radio bright with sufficiently high ratio of radio to optical B band flux [9] and categorized as radio-loud AGNs. Gamma-ray loud AGNs are

even fewer. Wavelength dependent AGN classification schemes for example, radio-selected, X-ray selected and gamma-ray selected are very popular classifications and often discussed in literature. The location of gamma or VHE gamma-rays in AGNs is still a topic of hot debate. However, it has been suggested that gamma-ray photons are likely to be produced when the plasma blob reaches BLR [10].

1.3 AGN Paradigm

The AGNs are highly puzzling sources as they show different behaviors and observational features. Their classification is very difficult and usually based on many things like strength of different observational parameters, radio morphology, etc. This naturally leads to an *AGN zoo* having sources of various names. After the discovery of Radio Astronomy, the earlier AGN classification schemes emerged based on their optical and radio observations. According to this *classification*, the sources are classified as Type 1, Type 2 and Type 3 AGNs.

Type 1 AGNs have broad emission lines in their optical spectra which arise due to high moving gas clouds closer to black hole. The radio quiet subclass of Type 1 AGN includes *Seyfert 1* galaxies and high luminosity radio quiet quasars. Radio loud Type 1 AGNs include low luminosity sources called *Broad Line Radio Galaxies (BLRGs)* while the high luminosity radio loud sources are referred as *Flat Spectrum Radio Quasars (FSRQs)* and *Steep Spectrum Radio Quasars (SSRQs)*, depending on the spectral index (α_r) in radio band.

Type 2 AGNs are active galaxies that only yield narrow emission line spectra. The radio quiet Type 2 AGNs include low luminosity *Seyfert 2* galaxies, while radio loud Type 2 are called *Narrow Line Radio Galaxies (NLRGs)*, including *Fanaroff-Riley (FR)* radio galaxies. FR radio galaxies are further divided into two types based on the radio morphology of relativistic jets. FR I galaxies have low luminosity and symmetric radio jets whose intensity decrease as moving away from the core. The

Figure 1. Fanaroff-Riley galaxies: Left panel shows the false colored image of FR II galaxy 3C98, while right panel shows the false colored image of FR I galaxy 3C 31. Source: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Radio_galaxy

high luminosity FR II galaxies demonstrate fainter but highly collimated jets which end up as bright hot-spots. The FR galaxies types are shown in Figure 1.

BL Lacertae (BL Lac) objects belong to Type 3 AGNs which are radio loud sources that lack broad line emission. However, they manifest narrow line emission like all other AGN types.

BL Lac and FSRQs are both luminous radio loud AGNs that have similar properties like continuum spectrum extending to gamma-rays, high polarization and rapid flux variability, so they together are called *Blazars*. The AGN classification based on radio loudness is shown by a grid in Figure 2.

Figure 2. AGN classification grid. [11]

1.4 Standard Model of AGN

Despite the fact that AGNs manifest different observational pointers, they still represent many similar properties. This fact leaves the room for so called *Unification Models*. The main AGN Paradigm is believed to consist of a *Supermassive Black Hole (SMBH)* surrounded by an *Accretion Disk* of hot gas, *Broad Line Region (BLR)*, *Narrow Line Region (NLR)* and an obscuring *Molecular Torus*. In AGN terminology, the compact object (a black hole) in the heart of nucleus, which is responsible for observed flux, is called *Central Engine* [12]. The Standard AGN Unification Model was put forward and explained by [12] and graphically depicted in Figure 3.

All types of AGNs are believed to be intrinsically same while their apparent differences arise due to obscuration by circumnuclear dusty torus [12]. The various types of radio loud AGNs are based on the radiation anisotropy or obscuration and orientation of radio jets. Figure 4 explains the AGN classification through unification scheme. The torus is a dense and thick doughnut consisting of opaque molecules. The light at IR to optical-UV wavelengths cannot escape through the

Figure 3. Standard model of Active Galactic Nuclei. [12]

Figure 4. AGN classification due to orientation effects. Based on [12]

doughnut and gets absorbed, then subsequently radiated by thermal emission. In the vicinity of black hole, there exist rapidly moving gaseous clouds. The region is called BLR. The clouds emit line spectra due to ionization of gas by the radiation. BLR remains hidden within dusty torus when viewed edge-on (parallel to plane of torus) and so the degree of obscuration decides whether an AGN is Type 1 or Type 2. The slow moving NLR clouds exist beyond the molecular torus and emit narrow emission lines. That is why narrow lines are present in every type of AGN. The radio loud AGN depict luminous radio jet streams perpendicular to disk plane, originating from compact core to kpc to Mpc away in the interstellar and intergalactic medium. These jets are produced by ejection of very high energy plasma knots by black hole. The morphology and brightness of these jets vary among different radio loud sub-types. When viewed edge on, these jets do not contribute significantly to the observed emission. This explains the high luminosity of Type 2 AGNs. Figure 4 gives graphical demonstration of unification model in terms of orientation effects.

2 Blazar Phenomenon

Blazars are highly beamed counterparts of radio loud AGNs that emit broadband nonthermal radiation towards earth. The BL Lac objects together with FSRQs, when their jets lying within small angles to line of sight, constitute to this class of objects. Blazars are one of the most energetic phenomenon observed in extragalactic universe. The bipolar relativistic AGN jets are highly collimated from kpc to Mpc scales [13]. Their composition, acceleration and collimation mechanisms have not been well established, see [14] for a review on the subject. The radiation from the jets gets boosted when lying within small angles to observer's line of sight. The schematic diagram of a plasma jet and its different emitting regions are shown in Figure 5. In many powerful blazars, the plasma knots ejected by black hole seem to move apparently with higher velocity than the speed of light. This phenomenon, called *Superluminal motion*, was put forward by [15]. The higher flux and short variability times of blazars are attributed to apparent superluminal motion relativistic motion of particles along the observer. This phenomenon can be understood by Figure 6. The plasma blob emitted by black hole moves with the speed $\beta = v/c$ in source frame making an angle θ with the line of sight. In observer's frame of reference, the apparent speed of knot $\beta_{app} = v_{app}/c$ can be calculated as:

$$\beta_{app} = \frac{\beta \sin \theta}{1 - \beta \cos \theta} \quad (3)$$

Here β and β_{app} are dimensionless quantities, as the particle velocities v and v_{app} are given in units of c . For relativistic particles with velocities approaching to speed of light and moving close to line of sight (smaller θ), the apparent velocities exceed the speed of light.

Beaming effects can explain the high luminosity, high degree of polarization and shorter variability time scales in blazars. The isotropically radiated power of relativistic plasma jet in the rest frame of particle is beamed in observer's rest [16]. The radiation from the relativistic incoming jet is enhanced by the the *Doppler*

Figure 5. Schematic cartoon of a relativistic jet and different emission zones in a radio loud AGN. The mm-core is the place where the jet appears bright in VLBI image. The distance from central black hole is presented in Schwarzschild radii R_s . Note that distance increases on logarithmic scale. Credits: Marscher, Alan. "Blazar Research Group, Institute for Astrophysical Research, Boston University", <http://www.bu.edu/blazars/research.html>, website, 25.5.2014

Figure 6. The plasma blob moving with relativistic speed β making angle θ with line of sight. When θ is small, the emission is boosted along line of sight.

factor as given by:

$$\delta = \frac{1}{\gamma(1 - \beta \cos \Theta)} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2} \quad (5)$$

is called *Lorentz factor* of the jet. The emission from a jet moving opposite to line of sight is de-boosted by the same factor. The frequency of incoming photons increases as $\nu = \delta\nu'$ and arrival time is changed to $\Delta t = \delta^{-1}\Delta t'$. Here primed quantities refer to source rest frame. For a comprehensive account of relativistic effects in blazars, see [17].

2.1 Radiation Mechanisms in Blazars

Generally any particle distribution in thermal equilibrium would emit a radiation called *blackbody radiation*. This radiation arise due to thermal excitation and de-excitation of the particles and not due to their interaction with electromagnetic fields. The UV radiation from the accretion disk is believed to be produced through this process. The radiation produced by the charged particles due to there acceleration and interaction with electromagnetic fields is called *nonthermal radiation*. These radiation mechanisms (for example synchrotron, Compton scattering, pair production, etc.) have been considered to be dominant mechanisms for observed radiation from blazar jets.

2.1.1 Sychrotron Radiation

Since the blazar jet consists or relativistic plasma, the presence of magnetic fields in astrophysical sources makes the field-particle interaction inevitable. The charged particles, entering in a magnetic field with arbitrary angles, are influenced by magnetic field and gyrate into helical paths around the field lines. The gyrating force is set up due to interaction of field and particle and called *Lorentz force*. The gyration

frequency ω of a relativistic electron of charge e and mass m , entering into a region of magnetic field B , is given by:

$$\omega = \frac{eB}{\gamma mc} \quad (6)$$

where $\gamma = (1 - \beta)^{-1/2}$ is electron Lorentz factor and c is the velocity of light.

The particles emit a radiation due to interaction with magnetic field called cyclotron radiation. When the injected particles are relativistic ($\beta \sim 1$), this radiation is called *Synchrotron radiation*. The radiative power emitted by an electron entering into a region of magnetic field at an angle ψ , called pitch angle, is given in [16] by following equation:

$$P_{syn} = \frac{2}{3} r_e^2 \gamma^2 \beta^2 B^2 \sin^2 \psi \quad (7)$$

where $r_e = e^2/mc^2$ is called classical electron radius. The radiative power of particle is inversely proportional to its mass, hence electrons are more efficient emitters of synchrotron radiation than protons.

Averaging over all the pitch angles, the synchrotron power emitted by an electron, as given in [16], becomes:

$$P_{syn} = \frac{4}{3} \beta^2 \gamma^2 c \sigma_T U_B \quad (8)$$

where σ_T is Thomson cross section of interaction and $U_B = B^2/8\pi$ is the energy density of magnetic field. Due to relativistic effects becoming important at high particle velocities (close to speed of light c), the radiation power emitted by electrons is squeezed into a narrow cone in direction of instantaneous velocity vector with an half-angle of $\theta \propto 1/\gamma$, as shown in Figure 7.

Generally stochastic acceleration processes in astrophysical sources produce a power law distribution of particles. When such a power law distribution described as $n(\gamma) = N_0 \gamma^{-p}$ (where $\gamma_{min} < \gamma < \gamma_{max}$) is submitted to synchrotron mechanism, the net frequency distribution of radiated power follows a power law form with spectral index $\alpha = \frac{-(p-1)}{2}$. At lower frequencies the photons are absorbed by electrons and the source becomes optically thick. This process is called *Synchrotron Self-Absorption*.

Figure 7. Doppler beaming of synchrotron radiation into a cone of opening angle θ . [18]

In self-absorption regime, the emitted synchrotron distribution has a spectral index of $5/2$. Following a turnover, the distribution becomes $\nu^{-\alpha}$, as shown in Figure 8. Thus the overall spectrum represents a broken power law changing from $\nu^{5/2}$ to $\nu^{-(p-1)/2}$. Synchrotron emission is highly polarized and this fact makes it easy to rule out thermal radiation mechanisms in AGNs.

2.1.2 Inverse Compton Radiation

The process, in which low energy electrons are scattered by highly energetic photons, is called *Compton Scattering* and its opposite process, in which low energy photons are up-scattered by high energy electrons, is called *Inverse Compton(IC) Scattering*. The relativistic electrons share their momentum with soft photons, blue-shifting their frequency and energy.

Figure 8. The synchrotron spectrum of power law electrons. The optically thick regime follows $\nu^{5/2}$, while the optically thin radiation follows $\nu^{-\alpha}$ or $\nu^{-(p-1)/2}$. Credits: Williams, Jonathan. "Institute for Astronomy, University of Hawaii", <http://www.ifa.hawaii.edu/~jpw/classes/ast622.spring2008/handouts/synchrotron.html>, website, 25.5.2014

If the energy of incident photon in electron rest frame is less than electron rest mass energy (*i.e.* $\gamma E \ll mc^2$), the energy of scattered photons becomes $E_s = \gamma^2 E$ and the scattering cross-section of scattering is given by classical Thomson approximation as:

$$\frac{d\sigma_T}{d\Omega} = \frac{1}{2} r_e^2 (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \quad (9)$$

where r_e^2 is classical electron radius, θ is the angle between incident and scatter photon rays and Ω is the scattering solid angle. In Thomson scattering, the electron recoil is neglected and the energy gain becomes very large for higher Lorentz factors. At higher photon energies, such that $\gamma E \gg m_e c^2$, the electron recoil becomes important and quantum mechanical effects must be included in order to compute the scattering cross-section. In such cases, the total cross-section is described by Klein-Nishina formula as given by:

$$\frac{d\sigma_{KN}}{d\Omega} = \frac{r_e^2 E_s^2}{2 E^2} \left(\frac{E}{E_s} + \frac{E_s}{E} - \sin^2 \theta \right) \quad (10)$$

In Thomson scattering, even the higher photon energy gain is just a fraction of

electron energy. However in Klein-Nishina limit, the electrons lose almost entire energy and the energy of scattered photon becomes $E_s = \gamma m_e c^2$. Since $\sigma_{KN} < \sigma_T$, the radiated power is diminished at extreme photon energies.

In case of a single IC event, the IC radiative power of an electron, assuming Thomson cross-section, is given by:

$$P_c = \frac{4}{3} \beta^2 \gamma^2 c \sigma_T U_{ph} \quad (11)$$

Where U_{ph} is the energy density of photons.

In nonthermal radiation models, synchrotron and IC scattering are main channels of cooling the particle population. The ratio of synchrotron to IC radiative power can be given as:

$$\frac{P_s}{P_c} = \frac{U_B}{U_{ph}} \quad (12)$$

This relation shows that relative strength of these radiative processes depends upon ratio of radiation and magnetic densities. The scattering in Klein-Nishina regime does not contribute significantly to IC luminosity of the source due to suppression of cross-section.

The IC scattering, where target photons to be scattered are synchrotron photons of same source, is called *Synchrotron Self-Compton (SSC)* [19]. SSC scattering is naturally an inevitable process in compact sources such as blazars. Since the SSC emission arise due to same electron distribution and synchrotron radiation, the shape of IC spectra remains same as that of synchrotron emission. Besides SSC, there are many suggested external sources of soft seed photons for inverse Compton scattering of injected electrons. In this case the scattering process is called *External Compton (EC)*, and source of photons can be accretion disk [20], BLR [21] or dusty torus [22].

2.2 Spectral Energy Distribution

After the discovery of gamma-rays from 3C 279 in 1991 [23], it has been revealed that blazars are broad band energy emitters and the study of AGNs entered into a new era where it is now possible to study the spectral distribution of the sources from radio to gamma-rays. The ground based radio telescopes (Effelsberg, Metsähovi, OVRO, NRAO, etc.) and interferometers like VLA or VLBI, optical telescopes (Tuorla optical telescope, HST, VLT, Swift UVOT, etc.), X-rays telescopes (Swift XRT/BAT, XMM Newton, etc.) and gamma to VHE gamma telescopes and arrays (like INTEGRAL, Fermi, H.E.S.S, MAGIC, etc.) provide the wealth of multifrequency data to construct *Spectral Energy Distribution (SED)* of these sources.

The SED is a popular method of representation of broadband data in $\log(\nu)$ vs $\log(\nu F_\nu)$ form. Generally units used for frequency ν and flux F_ν are Hz and $\text{erg}/\text{cm}^{-2}/\text{s}$ respectively. The term $\log(\nu F_\nu)$ gives the logarithmic spectral flux. The advantage of this term over $\log(F_\nu)$ is that the high steepness of spectrum is diminished and a smooth variation appear in the plot. Since blazars are highly variable sources, the simultaneous observations are very important to understand the underlying physics of emission.

The typical SED of a Blazar shows two bumps in the broadband SED. In leptonic jet models the low energy emission arise due to synchrotron radiation, thus the low energy bump is called synchrotron peak, while the higher energy peak is referred as inverse Compton peak. In SSC models, the higher peak is assumed to appear due to scattering of same synchrotron photons and referred as SSC peak. Figure 9 shows the SED of source 3C 279. The synchrotron peak frequency ν_s is very important parameter in understanding emission mechanisms and AGN Physics. For FSRQs, ν_s usually appear somewhere between radio to optical (usually at IR) region and generally $< 10^{14}$ Hz. The BL Lacs with synchrotron peak in IR-to-optical ($10^{14} < \nu_s < 10^{15}$) range are called *Low frequency BL Lacs (LBLs)* or *Intermediate BL*

Figure 9. Simultaneous SED of 3C 279. The red symbols represent simultaneous observations, whereas the grey points represent the archival data. [24]

Table 1. Blazar Classification based on Synchrotron peak ν_s .

Synchrotron peak (Hz)	Source Type
$\nu_s < 10^{14}$	LSP
$10^{14} < \nu_s < 10^{15}$	ISP
$\nu_s > 10^{15}$	HSP

Lacs (IBLs). Those BL Lac objects having ν_s between UV and X-rays ($> 10^{15}$) are termed as *High frequency BL Lacs (HBLs)*. This blazar terminology was introduced by [25] and frequently referred in the literature.

A newer *Blazar Classification*, described by [26], is solely based on location of synchrotron peak ν_s and may help in blazar unification models. According to this criteria, the different blazars are strictly classified into *Low Synchrotron Peak (LSP)*, *Intermediate Synchrotron Peak (ISP)* and *High Synchrotron peak (HSP)* sources, based on the position of their synchrotron peak ν_s in the SED, irrespective of whether they be a quasar or BL Lac. This classification is summarized in Table 1.

The log parabolic fitting of synchrotron SEDs is often employed to find the synchrotron peak of the sources, as in case of [27] and [28]. However, more realistic

and physical models generally do not consider fitting the low energy spectra (Radio-to-IR) smoothly and, thus, the synchrotron peaks may get exaggerated. The peaks measured by the employed one-zone SSC model may be slightly exaggerated and very closely match to those reported by [29], as they used same SED data as used in this work.

Generally all blazars do not have similar SED shapes. SED shapes of various sources show a continuous sequence, called *Blazar Sequence*. This sequence was put forward by [30] arguing that the luminosity and synchrotron peak frequency are inter-related. Before emergence of this sequence, [31] reported that a continuity is observed in SED shape of various sources (including Radio selected BL Lacs (RBLs), X-ray selected BL Lacs (XBLs) and FSRQs), which cannot be solely interpreted due to change in viewing angle but needs a systematic change in physical jet parameters like source size, magnetic field and electron Lorentz factor.

According to blazar sequence, the sources with high gamma-ray luminosity possess lower synchrotron peak frequencies (also vice versa) and the luminosity ratio of IC peak to synchrotron peak increases with bolometric luminosity. The ratio of IC to synchrotron peak is called *Compton dominance*. The blazar sequence is shown in Figure 10 and can be summarized as fact that the high Compton dominated sources seem to have lower synchrotron peak frequencies than less dominated source. The theoretical interpretation of this observed sequence was made by [32], according to whom, HBLs are lowest luminous objects due to weaker external radiation field. Consequently, the injected particles can emit synchrotron radiation to larger values of ν_s without any scattering from photons. LBLs are intrinsically more powerful than HBLs and external photons can contribute to higher observed luminosity in some objects. FSRQs are the most powerful sources in which external radiation photons strongly contribute and are responsible for their higher Compton domination. Due to presence of strong external cooling in these sources, the synchrotron

Figure 10. Blazar sequence shown as a continuity in $\log(\nu)$ - $\log(\nu L_\nu)$ space. [30]

emitting population cannot reach UV or X-rays. Thus, the theoretical interpretation of blazar sequence [32] implies that EC modelling of FSRQs is favorable.

3 Blazar SSC Modelling

Blazar models are theoretically constructed to estimate the entire blazar emission in terms of interaction between radiation and matter assuming different radiation mechanisms. These blazar emission models can be leptonic or hadronic.

Generally, in leptonic emission models, the entire emission (SED) of a blazar is produced through synchrotron emission and inverse Compton cooling of energetic electrons via either the same electrons (SSC) [33] or external photons (EC). In hadronic models, the higher energy spectra (usually gamma to VHE gamma-rays) are produced by proton synchrotron radiation [34] or proton induced cascades [35]. Hadronic models need higher magnetic field values and much higher particle energies as compared to SSC models due to fact that protons are heavier and thus slower particles than electrons. Leptonic models are favored over hadronic ones due to fact that they can explain the entire SED of a source self-consistently and particle energies required are achievable from shock acceleration processes. A good review of leptonic and hadronic blazar modelling, see [36].

In *leptonic SSC models*, the relativistic electrons ($\gamma \gg 1$), assuming a mono-energetic, power law or broken power law distribution, are accelerated and injected into a radiative zone where they lose energy through sychrotron mechanism and get cooled. The same sychrotron photons are up-scattered to higher energies by same electrons via IC scattering and, thus, gets further cooled. In principle, multiple inverse Compton scatterings of synchrotron photons are possible unless the particle population is cooled below a threshold energy value. These models are numerically implemented usually to compute the radiative losses in order to account for observed SED of nonthermal sources and constrain the emission parameters like magnetic field, electron density, particle energy and size of the source.

Generally the SSC models are successful in fitting the observed spectra of TeV BL Lacs (HBLs in particular) adequately, as discussed in [37] and [38]. This is due

Figure 11. SSC model fit to 1ES 2344+514 SED. The triangles represent the high state simultaneous 2007 observations while circles show the time averaged and moderate state data on 1 January 2008. The open circles, triangles and squares represent historical data. [39]

to fact that TeV HBL sources do not seem to have strong BLR contribution to IC luminosity. Many SSC models with different theoretical considerations about shape of particle population and source geometry have been used in the past to understand the radiation mechanisms and conditions involved in production of bulk emission from blazars. For illustration, the SSC model fit in case of source 1ES 2344+514 [39] is shown in Figure 11. The leptonic SSC models, however, have been failed to account for the observed SEDs in quasars like 3C 279 [40], especially when these sources are flaring. Usually gamma and VHE gamma emission in many gamma-ray loud AGNs cannot be modelled with SSC approach, because at higher photons energies, efficiency of SSC models is reduced by Klein-Nishina effects. According to blazar sequence, FSRQs and LBLs are LSP sources with higher gamma-ray fluxes than HSP BL Lacs (HBLs). This suggests that the models which are useful for HBLs may not work in case of FSRQs or LBLs. In FSRQs, there is a significant BLR contribution at optical-UV bands and these photons can be used for external Compton (EC) scattering. EC models have been successfully used over the decades

to model the SEDs of quasars, especially when flaring.

The location of gamma-rays is very important while proposing realistic models for blazar emission but still appears to be a much debated issue in concerned circles. If gamma-ray emission arises outside the dusty torus, then the strong BLR contribution to IC can be ruled out and SSC must be sufficient to meet the observations. Usually gamma-ray and low frequency emission at radio frequency may assumed to be produced by different emitting regions at different locations, as the radio emission arises from extended regions in the jet. If the gamma-ray emission is also produced in the extended radio knots due to shocks, then a pure SSC approach would seem more convincing than EC. In this way EC can be ruled out at extended regions due to lack of powerful seed photons field outside the BLR. The location of emitting region is important to constrain the physical parameters like source size, magnetic field, electron density and Lorentz factor.

3.1 Non-linear SSC Model

SSC is unavoidably a favorite process for high energy radiation as the synchrotron photons can be the best available targets to relativistic electron. It has been commonly observed in many high state nonthermal blazars that the most of their radiated power lies in the high energy SSC peak, which dominates the synchrotron peak. This is particularly true for LSP sources (especially FSRQs) and implies that, in these sources, the inverse Compton (SSC) losses are at least equal or greater than synchrotron losses. The *Compton dominance* can be measured as the ratio of SSC to synchrotron losses, as described in [41]. The SSC models usually fail to account for higher Compton dominance in LSP sources, suggesting that a higher order SSC cooling term must be used. The time dependent nonlinear SSC cooling term in Thomson limit, as furnished by [42], stating that the SSC loss rate depends on energy integral of electron population.

The nonlinear SSC model assumes the spherical and homogeneous nonthermal source with instantaneous injection of mono-energetic electrons of energy γ_0 into radiation blob, subjected to combined nonlinear SSC and linear synchrotron cooling. This injection corresponds to a complete flaring event and does not represent the steady state.

The competition between an arbitrary injection distribution function $Q(\gamma)$ and total radiative loss term $|\dot{\gamma}|_{tot}$, for a relativistic electron population, is described by volume averaged time-dependent kinetic equation, presented in [43] as:

$$\frac{\partial n(\gamma, t)}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \gamma} \{ |\dot{\gamma}|_{tot} n(\gamma, t) \} = Q(\gamma, t) \quad (13)$$

where γ is particle energy, $n(\gamma, t)$ denotes volume averaged differential electron number density and $Q(\gamma, t) = q_0 \delta(\gamma - \gamma_0) \delta(t)$ is the source term for mono-energetic electron injection. The total loss rate in terms of synchrotron and SSC cooling rates is given in [43] as:

$$|\dot{\gamma}|_{TOT} = |\dot{\gamma}|_S + |\dot{\gamma}|_{SSC} \quad (14)$$

or

$$|\dot{\gamma}|_{TOT} = D_0 \gamma^2 + A_0 \gamma^2 \int_0^\infty d\gamma \gamma^2 n(\gamma, t) \quad (15)$$

Where D_0 and A_0 are constants.

A complete description of combined linear synchrotron and nonlinear SSC modelling is constructed by Zacharias and Schlickeiser [43] and reveals that SSC loss rate of the electron depends on the energy integral of the actual electron spectrum $n(\gamma, t)$, suggesting that SSC cooling term is nonlinear and time dependent. This dependence of cooling rate on the energy integral is a collective effect which is completely different from linear synchrotron loss rate of the electron. Since the high energy electrons will be severely cooled, any broad electron distribution will be quenched into a mono-energetic one swiftly. This implies that mono-energetic approach is at least valid for later times. Due to time dependency, the SSC cooling rate decreases over time as

electrons lose energy, implying that SSC is strong cooling mechanism initially and the linear synchrotron cooling will eventually dominate.

This nonlinear SSC model (hereafter referred as ZS model) purely relies on instantaneous mono-energetic injection of electrons into radiative zone. It has been extended to light curve modelling using combined cooling scenario [44], complementing a complete picture of the model. Since nonlinear cooling terms make the particle effectively cool at higher energies, the model predicts very steep spectra at gamma-rays. [45] extended the nonlinear SSC model by including EC cooling of BLR to account for high energy emission, however such treatment is avoided in this work.

3.1.1 Injection Parameter

It has been established that solutions of kinetic equation depend on injection parameter α [43], as given by:

$$\alpha = \frac{|\gamma(t=0)|_{SSC}}{|\gamma|_S} = \gamma_0 \sqrt{\frac{q_0 A_0}{D_0}} \quad (16)$$

The injection parameter α is defined as the ratio of nonlinear cooling term to the linear cooling term at the time of injection ($t = 0$). It is proportional to density of electrons q_0 injected in the radiation zone. Nonlinear cooling will prevail for higher values of q_0 . Increasing α predicts a significant increase in gamma-ray luminosity, thus nonlinear model can be efficiently used in modelling extreme flares where gamma-ray flux increases by few orders of magnitude or orphan gamma-ray flares.

The α describes the Compton dominance in terms of initial electron injection conditions of the source, suggesting that either nonlinear SSC cooling or linear synchrotron cooling sets in initially. The shape of SEDs in ZS model depends on initial Klein-Nishina parameter K [43] and its value becomes:

$$K = 0.136b\gamma_4^3 \quad (17)$$

Figure 12. Model SED for nonlinear SSC cooling in Thomson regime $K \ll 1$. [43]

While b is the magnetic field strength and γ_4 is described in terms of initial electron Lorentz factor γ_0 as $\gamma_0 = 10^4 \gamma_4$. K is $\ll 1$ for initial Thomson limit, while in initial Klein-Nishina limit, $K \gg 1$. For extreme Klein-Nishina limit $1 \ll \alpha^3 \ll K$ [43].

For large density of injected electrons, $\alpha \gg 1$ and SSC cooling rate dominates (cooling becomes initially nonlinear) and higher Compton domination is recovered. For $\alpha \ll 1$, the synchrotron peak dominates the observed spectrum. These results in Thomson limit are shown in Figure 12. The injection parameter does not only control the Compton dominance but the shape of SED as well. For $\alpha \ll 1$, the synchrotron peak shows a single power law ($\nu^{1/2}$) and an exponential cutoff. For $\alpha \gg 1$ in Thomson regime, SSC peak shows a power law ($\nu^{3/4}$) and follows an exponential cutoff. In Klein-Nishina regime, the SSC spectrum represents a double power law with a break at Schlickeiser–Röken energy [42]. For complete analytical treatment and description of nonlinear SSC cooling, see [41] and [43].

Concluding, higher the density q_0 of injected particles into blob yields higher α , leading to nonlinear radiative cooling initially, and higher Compton dominance is recovered. This is an important implication of combined cooling scenario involving nonlinear SSC and linear synchrotron cooling mechanisms in blazar modelling. It shows that the nonlinear SSC model is able to account for high gamma-ray fluxes,

as observed in flaring sources, and interpret such high fluxes due to higher injection of particles into source. This is obviously contradictory to the EC models, using external photon components to account for high gamma-ray flux.

The other parameters include the Doppler factor δ , magnetic field B in Gauss, Lorentz factor of injected electrons γ_0 and $Norm$ which takes into account size and distance effects. I assume only single value of particle energy γ_0 to produce SED due to mono-energetic distribution. The mono-energetic electron injection is justified as any power law distribution will be quenched into narrow mono-energetic like distribution at later times [43].

Higher values of γ shift the entire spectrum to higher frequencies reducing the SSC luminosity due to decrease in particle cross-section. To compensate this luminosity suppression, α should also increase while increasing γ . The $Norm$ parameter can be adjusted to increase or decrease the source luminosity, whereas same can be achieved by adjusting Doppler factor δ through boosting or de-boosting of radiation.

3.2 Data

Usually various dedicated simultaneous multifrequency observation campaigns are organized to study the spectral and broadband behavior of AGN. Since blazars are extremely variable sources, the simultaneous observations are very important to understand the physical picture. This is especially true for the flaring states where the variability time scales usually become shorter than the quiescent states. This is, however, not always possible due to atmospheric and observational constraints and many times non-simultaneous or quasi-simultaneously SEDs are available.

I have used the simultaneous multifrequency *Planck*, *Swift* and *Fermi LAT* data, including many ground based radio and optical telescopes, published in [28], to model the selected sample of sources. The multifrequency data covers entire broad-

Table 2. Summary of blazar sampling presented in [28].

Energy Band	Limiting flux	Catalog	5GHz flux limit	Reference
0.1 – 2.4 keV	0.3 counts s ⁻¹	ROSAT/RASS	200 mJy	[46]
15 – 150 keV	10 ⁻¹¹ erg cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	Swift BAT	100 mJy	[47]
> 100 MeV	8 × 10 ⁻⁸ ph cm ⁻² s ⁻¹	Fermi LBAS	1 Jy	[48]

band spectrum and is available at ASI¹ data center. The observation campaign selected the sources based on limiting flux in Soft and Hard X-rays and gamma-rays band, and complemented by 5 GHz flux limits to ensure good *Planck* detection [29]. Table 2 summarizes the sampling scheme of [28] in terms of limiting flux. The flux limits make sure that the source is bright in radio, X-rays and gamma-rays.

The sample is additionally constrained by Metsähovi 37 GHz Radio telescope flux limit of > 1 Jy. Such sampling based of limiting flux in various energy bands doesn't affect the SED modelling, however it affects the shape of the SED and produces the biases in statistical studies of AGNs [28].

I also study the SED of Fermi bright blazars observed by multifrequency campaign [26], including first 3 months data for LAT Bright AGN Sample (LBAS) from August to October 2008 [48]. The other data from Swift and many ground based observatories is gathered from May 2008 to January 2009. The data presented in this paper is quasi simultaneous (or non-simultaneous in some cases) and covers SED from radio to GeV gamma-rays. Such data sets can be misleading regarding real physical modelling and constraining the parameters, but useful to test the potential of the ZS model. The multifrequency light curves for selected sample of sources are also presented in this work to study the flaring behavior of the source. These include Metsähovi radio observatory 37 GHz unpublished, Tuorla 1 meter optical R-band²,

¹<http://www.asdc.asi.it/SED>

²Nilsson, Kari. "Optical light curves of blazars", <http://users.utu.fi/kani/1m/>, website, 25.5.2014

Swift X-rays [49] and Fermi gamma-ray³ light ray curves.

The flux data is usually published in different units for radio, optical, X-rays and gamma-rays. The published data is converted to SED νF_ν form with units $\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The radio data is published in Jansky (Jy) and converted to SED by using identity $1 \text{ Jy} = 10^{-23} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1}$. The optical data from Swift UVOT is published as magnitudes in its V, B, U, UVW1, UVM2 and UVW2 pass bands and converted to fluxes using standard zero points described in [50]. The Swift XRT data is published in $\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ units in 0.1 – 2.4 keV and 3 – 10 keV bands. The Fermi data is published as counts $10^{-10} \text{ photons cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{ MeV}^{-1}$ in its GeV bands. The SED is simply obtained by multiplying differential flux $\phi(E)$ of band by square of band energy E , i.e, $E^2\phi(E)$ [26].

The classification of different blazars is based on the carefully checked and compiled Roma-BZCAT catalog [51], which differentiate the Blazars into BZQ (FSRQs) and BZB (BL Lacs) and BZU (unidentified) sources, depending on the nature and strength of their optical spectra. This classification is oversimplified, however for sake of simplicity same classification scheme is used in this work.

³Fossati, Giovanni. "Fermi Monitored List", http://clownfish.rice.edu/~gfossati/Fermi/monitored_objects/, website, 25.5.2014

4 Blazar SED modelling

In this section, the physical modelling of selected blazar SEDs and its implications are described. The data from literature and archives are collected and plotted using numerical code⁴ based on ZS model. The parameter values are determined by reproducing the observed data, and various SED fits for a source are produced by varying and adjusting the model parameters. In principle, many similar model fits can be produced by different sets of parameters, however, only the best fits are presented in this work. These best fits are selected based simply on visual inspection.

The one-zone modelling assumes that all the emission arises from injection of mono-energetic particle blob into jet. I also model the blazar SEDs using multiple synchrotron components to account for entire multiwavelength emission in those cases where one-zone modelling doesn't seem to produce significant results. In multi-zone modelling, the observed SED is produced as a sum of individual SSC components. However only one-zone modelling is considered to study the source parameters and observe any correlations between them.

For a few frequently studied sources like 3C 454.3, 3C 279, BL Lac, PKS 2155-304, Mrk 501 and Mrk 421, multiple data sets corresponding to various multifrequency observation campaigns are compiled from literature are modelled. Since multiple similar fits can be achieved by varying the parameters, it is not easy to constrain the parameters. Therefore, to constrain the other parameters, the Doppler factor values are taken from [52] and [53] which report higher Doppler factors for FS-RQs and lower for BL Lacs. Since Doppler factor can be wavelength dependent [54] and vary from one observing episode to other, the used Doppler factor values may not be realistic.

⁴Tammi, Joni. "zs_ssc: Zacharias & Schlickeiser (2012) SSC model (version 1.1)", BitBucket, https://bitbucket.org/jptammi/zs_ssc/, website, 25.5.2014

4.1 3C 454.3

The FSRQ 3C 454.3 at a redshift of $z = 0.859$ is among the most frequently studied galactic nuclei in the last decade due to its extreme variable behaviour across the entire electromagnetic spectrum. It produced some very powerful outbursts in the last decade, for example 2007 gamma-ray flare, as seen by AGILE [55] and [56]. It was one of the brightest gamma-ray source detected on the sky during its November 2010 flare in *Fermi* $E > 100$ MeV band with the peak Fermi LAT flux of 85×10^{-6} photons $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ [57]. The flare was observed in all spectral bands ranging from radio to gamma-rays and by a dedicated multifrequency campaign [58].

4.1.1 2009 SED Modelling

I plot 14 December 2009 SED for 3C 454.3, corresponding to Modified Julian Date (MJD) 55180), including published simultaneous Planck, Swift and Fermi data [28]. The source experienced a powerful outburst at all wavelengths in November 2009. The December 2009 multifrequency emission modelled data corresponds to post flaring state of the source, as shown by Figure 13. While 37 GHz band, on behalf of Planck, shows the early growing stage of the biggest radio flare ever before, the optical to gamma-ray regime shows post flaring (declining) states of the source. This shows that lower and higher energy bands do not correlate.

The nonlinear SSC model, as shown by solid curve in Figure 14, is able to approximate the observed IR-to-optical flux with X-rays slightly lower than observed. The model poorly fits the radio-IR data poorly while MeV-GeV range seems to be slightly overestimated. However, such higher fluxes cannot be ruled out due to lack to observation in this band. Fermi LAT gamma-rays cannot be explained by the one-zone SSC at all. This implies that the radio-IR growing flare cannot be modelled consistently post flaring gamma-rays. If higher particle energy γ and α are assumed to account for entire IC peak, the IR to optical synchrotron emission has to be al-

Figure 13. Multifrequency light curve for 3C 454.3. Upper panel shows 37 GHz radio light curve curve with hatched region indicating the of Planck observations [29]. Lower panel shows optical, X-rays and gamma-ray light curves from top to bottom respectively [59]. The red line shows the date of simultaneous observations.

Figure 14. December 2009 SSC modelling of 3C 454.3 SED: The solid curve is normal fit to data while dashed curve represents the SSC fit to Compton peak. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(4, 33, 1, 3 \times 10^3, 3 \times 10^{-30})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(15, 33, 0.2, 7.5 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-31})$ for dashed curve.

together reduced, as shown by the dashed curve in Figure 14. This is because the higher α assumes the higher Compton dominance and, thus, even low synchrotron luminosity can produce the observed SSC luminosity due to nonlinear behavior of SSC term. This implies that a one-zone nonlinear SSC model cannot describe the entire SED of 3C 454.3 and the Fermi LAT gamma emission cannot be reproduced through SSC consistently with growing radio-IR synchrotron shock.

In November 2010, 3C 454.3 experienced a powerful flare. The pre- and post-flaring states SEDs of 3C 454.3 for December 2009 were modelled perfectly by [59] with an SSC model, also assuming EC of soft photons from BLR and accretion disk. Figure 15 shows their modelling of 2nd flare (followed by a giant flare) and post flaring state SEDs. The parameters used to model post flare SED are $B = 0.6$ Gauss, $R = 7 \times 10^{16}$, $\gamma_b = 800$ (break energy of electron spectrum) and $\gamma_{min} = 45$ (lower cutoff of electron spectra). I argue that nonlinear SSC model with mono-energetic spectra fails to explain observed 2009 post-flare SED of 3C 454.3 and replacing linear SSC relation by nonlinear SSC cooling does not produce sufficient

Figure 15. Secondary flare (blue filled squares) and post-flare spectra (gray open circles) for December 2010. For details, see text. [59]

fit to data.

Figure 16 shows that there should be no component between radio-IR to optical range and emphasizes that the gamma-ray emission must be produced by growing radio-IR shock [29]. In one-zone case, the entire synchrotron peak cannot be modelled. This is due to mono-energetic assumption of particles population, which cools rapidly due to non-linearity of cooling rate and entire peaks cannot be modelled.

The failure of one-zone SED fitting provides motivation for multi-zone SSC modelling of the source. Since there is a lack of correlation between radio-IR and Fermi gamma-ray flux as confirmed by the light curves, the multi-zone SSC modelling is favored. The radio emission seem to arise from a different particle distribution with much higher cooling time scales. The whole SED can be remarkably fit by a multi-zone SSC model and the gamma-rays can be consistently modelled. In case of multi-components SSC, the radio-IR synchrotron component accounts for observed X-rays levels while the IR-optical component accounts for gamma-rays, as shown by Figure 17(a). however only two components are added due to lack of data in this frequency range. Squeezing another IR synchrotron component can produce

Figure 16. Radio to optical SED of 3C 454.3. [29]

the MeV-GeV data without the need to sacrifice the Fermi data and fits the entire SED from radio to gamma-rays, as shown in Figure 17(b). All this implies that multi-zone modelling should be considered for December 2009 state of of 3C 454.3 as shown in Figure 17.

(a) 2 zone SSC modelling of 3C 454.3. The solid curve is model fit to SED while the dashed (colored) curves show individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.63, 33, 0.1, 1 \times 10^3, 1.5 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.8, 33, 0.4, 5 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-29})$ for cyan.

(b) 3 zone SSC modelling of 3C 454.3. The solid curve is model fit to SED while the dashed (colored) curves show individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.65, 33, 0.1, 9 \times 10^2, 1 \times 10^{-29})$ for red, $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.1, 33, 0.1, 3 \times 10^3, 1.6 \times 10^{-29})$ for cyan and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.8, 33, 0.1, 9 \times 10^3, 1.8 \times 10^{-29})$ for green.

Figure 17. 2009 multi-zone SSC modelling of 3C 454.3 SED.

4.1.2 2008 SED Modelling

I also model the quasi-simultaneous published data for 3C 454.3 gathered around August-October 2008 Fermi campaign [26]. This SED closely matches to the one for December 2009. For this epoch, the radio light curve shows a decay of a powerful radio flare and optical to Fermi light ray curves also represents quiescent state. The multifrequency light curve is shown in Figure 18.

In this case, as depicted by a solid curve in Figure 19, the SSC model again fails to fit the entire SED of the source. The model fit shows that IR-optical synchrotron emitting population is responsible for observed SSC soft X-rays to soft gamma-rays. However, Fermi GeV gamma-rays cannot be produced consistently in the same radiation zone. The model assumes lesser contribution from radio-IR shock. Any attempt to fit entire SSC peak including gamma-rays would assume the higher injection parameter α and particle energy γ_0 , and thus, underproduce the synchrotron luminosity. Such SSC modelling is shown by dashed curve in Figure 19. This implies that nonlinear cooling cannot describe VHE gamma-ray emission in post flaring states with lesser Compton domination. The multi-zone SSC modelling of August 2008 explains the radio to gamma SED with two SSC components consistently. In quiescent states, it is more likely that the bulk of emission may arise due to many individual components, in agreement with [60] which studied the multifrequency variability correlation from July to December 2008 and found similar variability patterns in IR, optical and gamma-ray bands, while X-rays didn't seem to have little variability with no correlation, as shown by Figure 21. This indicates that optical, X-rays and gamma-rays arise in a compact region, whereas radio and X-ray emission mainly arise from dilute region with different source parameters. While [60] suggests that gamma-rays can be produced by external photons of accretion disk or BLR, two-zone ZS model can account for gamma-rays in SSC context. Even well within BLR, the SSC mechanism cannot be ruled out altogether. In

Figure 18. Multifrequency light curve of 3C 454.3 from April 2008 to April 2010 . From top to bottom: green (Metsähovi radio observatory 37 GHz), red (Tuorla 1m optical telescope R band), blue (Swift XRT 2 – 10 keV) and pink (Fermi LAT).

Figure 19. 2008 SSC modelling of 3C 454.3 SED: The solid curve is a normal fit to data while dashed curve represents the SSC fit to Compton peak. The parameters used are: $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(3.5, 33, 0.4, 3.5 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-30})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(10, 33, 0.04, 1 \times 10^4, 4 \times 10^{-31})$ for dashed curve.

Figure 20. 2008 multi-zone SSC modelling of 3C454.3 SED: The solid curve is model fit to SED while the dashed (colored) curves show individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.6, 33, 0.02, 4 \times 10^3, 8 \times 10^{-30})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(2.4, 33, 0.1, 7 \times 10^3, 3 \times 10^{-30})$ for cyan.

Figure 21. Multiwavelength light curves of 3C 454.3 at (top panel) gamma-ray (0.1–300 GeV), UV (W1), optical (B), and IR (J) wavelengths from Fermi/LAT, Swift UVOT, and SMARTS. X-rays (XRT) in lower panel. The IR/optical/UV variations are well correlated with the gamma-ray variations, with a lag of less than 1 day, while the (minimal) X-rays variability is uncorrelated. [60]

multi-zone modelling, the synchrotron IR-optical and SSC gamma-rays arise from a compact region with higher electron density while a less energetic SSC zone accounts for X-rays, as shown in Figure 20. In multi-zone modelling the GeV break is nicely matched due to a higher α and γ_0 in compact region.

4.1.3 2010 Flare SED Modelling

3C 454.3 underwent an extreme flare in November through December 2010, as seen by multiwavelength AGILE, Swift, INTEGRAL and GASP-WEBT campaign [58]. The flare erupted simultaneously at all wavelengths and gave possibility of simultaneous multifrequency observations. The flare peaks at MJD 55520 being the most violent in the gamma-ray regime, increasing the flux by a factor of 10 compared to pre-flaring state [58].

Figure 22. November 2010 flare one-zone SSC of 3C 454.3 SED: The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(2.4, 33, 0.07, 5.5 \times 10^3, 1.5 \times 10^{-29})$

I used the multifrequency published data for brightest day of November 2010 flaring [61] and modelled the source SED with the numerical SSC code. The one-zone ZS model reproduces the flare SED for 3C 454.3 November 2010 flare well, as shown in Figure 22. The nonlinear SSC is expected in this case, as such a giant flare might swamp all other older cooler blobs and the entire observed spectrum would arise due to freshly injected particle population. The 2010 flare SED of the source was also modelled by [43] with same model, as shown in Figure 23, assuming different parameters compared to one presented here (lower Doppler factor used). They use higher values of α because their data represent the higher gamma-ray state of the flare compared to data used in this work. Generally Compton domination seems to vary from beginning to end of the flare.

The November 2010 modelling of 3C 454.3 by [61] states that a same electron population is responsible for radio to UV synchrotron and X-rays to gamma-ray emission due to a co-relation between IR and gamma bands flux variations. My one-zone ZS modelling with single electron energy γ_0 complies with implications of variability pattern and fits fairly to source SED. This reveals that in such sort

Figure 23. November 2010 flare one-zone SSC of 3C 454.3 SED. [43]

of intense flares, the nonlinear SSC cooling term with a mono-energetic electron population should be considered in place of linear SSC relations with power law distributions. The high gamma-ray flux may not be always due to enhanced external radiation but possibly due to higher injection of particles initially in the jet.

4.1.4 Discussion

The high energy bands of Fermi are not easy to model and the fit gets steeper after 10^{24} Hz. However, squeezing extra SSC components can fit the observed GeV curvature. The 3C 454.3 August 2008 SED has been modelled by [62], which argued that GeV break in Fermi spectra cannot be explained by SSC only and employed a multi-component model to reproduce gamma-rays from external radiation (BLR). In their modelling, the SSC component fits the observed X-rays level and fails to account for such a large gamma-ray flux. The parameters used to calculate the SSC spectra in Figure 24 are $\delta = 28$, $B = 0.032$ G, $\gamma_{min} = 10$, $\gamma_{max} = 2 \times 10^9$ and $\gamma_{break} = 10^4$. Another modelling scheme [63] used BLR photons scattering with log parabolic electron distribution to model the August 2008 SED of 3C 454.3 and explains the GeV break in the spectrum due to Klein-Nishina effects on Compton

scattering. In one-zone ZS modelling, the SSC fits the X-rays to soft gamma-ray

Figure 24. SED of 3C 454.3. The model components for the multi-component model are shown as dashed curves, where the purple dashed curve is the Shakura–Sunyaev disk, the red is the synchrotron, the green is the SSC, the blue is the Compton-scattered disk, and the brown is the Compton-scattered BLR component. The thick dotted curve gives the SSC fit, and the thick solid curve shows the multi-component model. The inset shows the Fermi-LAT spectrum in more detail. The arrows indicate the frequency of the spectral break. [62].

levels much better than that of [62], however the GeV Fermi LAT spectra cannot be fit at all and particles cool very rapidly in GeV bands. This is due to mono-energetic limitation of the model and yields that the electron spectra should be replaced by a more complex form. The shape of SED indicates that initial Klein-Nishina parameter is less than unity, thus the source can be modelled within Thomson regime. Also, the Klein-Nishina energies would introduce a sharp break in gamma-rays, which is not observed in 3C 454.3. Even in extreme gamma-ray flares as in case of November 2010, the source SED is modelled well within Thomson regime.

The multi-zone ZS modelling of 3C 454.3 can produce the Fermi gamma-rays consistently without EC. Since both of December 2009 and August 2008 SEDs correspond to quiescent or post flaring states, such states may consist of many older and newer radiating blobs. The multi-zone SSC modelling for FSRQ 3C 454.3 can

also be justified due to fact that the superluminal radio knots that flow along the jet are usually connected to IR-optical flaring and can potentially contribute to gamma-ray flares as well, as indicated by Very Large Baseline Array (VLBA) parsec jet study [64]. Due to longer cooling time scales at radio frequencies, it is likely that there may be many older knots at the time of observations which can contribute to emission at radio and higher frequencies.

I argue that nonlinear SSC modelling should be considered to model gamma-ray flares of 3C 454.3, especially where the simultaneous flaring in all the energy bands becomes a strong evidence of a single particle population. For quiescent states, where the multifrequency variability amplitudes do not correlate, multi-zone SSC modelling works better.

4.2 3C 279

The quasar 3C 279 is widely and extensively studied extragalactic object at a redshift of 0.356. Over the years, the source has been observed by various dedicated multiwavelength campaigns, for example [65] and [66]. It was the first gamma-ray loud blazar observed by Energetic gamma-ray Experiment Telescope (EGRET) in 1991 June [23].

4.2.1 2010 SED Modelling

I model the published simultaneous Planck, Swift and Fermi multifrequency data complemented by earth based radio observatories for 15 January 2010 corresponding to MJD 55211 [28]. From Figure 25, it is clear that Metsähovi 37 GHz light curve shows a grown stage of a flare while Tuorla optical, Swift X-rays and Fermi gamma-ray light curves show low state of the source.

The radio-IR plack synchrotron SED snapshot of the 3C 279 presented by [29], as shown in Figure 26, shows that there should be no additional component in the

Figure 25. Multifrequency light curve for 3C279 from April 2008 to April 2010 . From top to bottom: green (Metsähovi radio observatory 37 GHz), red (Tuorla 1m optical telescope R band), blue (Swift XRT 2 – 10 keV) and pink (Fermi LAT).

Figure 26. Radio to optical SED of 3C 279. red circles, Low Frequency (LF) data simultaneous to Planck; blue circles, High Frequency (HF) data simultaneous to Planck. [29]

radio-IR to optical-UV frequency range and gamma-ray might arise from the same growing radio flare as shown in Figure 25(a). The SED model fit of 3C 279 with one-zone SSC code, as shown in Figure 27, shows that radio-IR to optical synchrotron regime and Fermi gamma-ray emission cannot be produced from the same particle population. The multifrequency light curves do not show similar variability pattern between radio and high energy bands. The optical to gamma-ray level belongs to quiescent state while source is highly active in radio-IR energy bands, as shown in Figure 25.

The one-zone model cannot account for such low level of Fermi gamma-rays whereas the radio-IR synchrotron flux is severely underproduced. The model yields much narrower peaks due to monoenergetic electron distribution. Modelling entire broad SSC peak would assume much higher injection parameter ($\alpha \gg 1$) and electron Lorentz factor, which would grossly underproduce entire synchrotron levels from radio through optical-UV, as shown by dotted curve in Figure 27. It all implies

Figure 27. 2010 one-zone SSC modelling of 3C 279 SED: the solid curve is normal fit to data while dashed curve represents the SSC fit to Compton peak. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (3.7, 24, 1.5, 2.4 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-30})$ for solid and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (10, 24, 0.3, 5.5 \times 10^3, 1.5 \times 10^{-31})$ for dashed curve.

that nonlinear SSC cooling with mono-energetic particle distribution cannot account the broadband SED of 3C 279 in quiescent state. The dashed SSC fit in Figure 27 can also be interpreted in this way, that if entire Compton peak emerge due to SSC, the synchrotron emission should be lower than observed.

The observed high level of radio-IR synchrotron emission can be attributed to newer shocks or a completely different radiating blob. Thus, the complete SED modelling in mono-energetic SSC context requires additional synchrotron components, especially to account for high radio-IR flux. In multi-zone ZS SSC model, the gamma emission may arise from a compact IR-optical component ($\alpha = 2.7$) and an additional cooler radio-IR component yields X-rays, as shown in Figure 28. This shows that with multi-zone nonlinear SSC cooling, the gamma-ray levels in FSRQs can be achieved while many SSC models fail.

Figure 28. 2010 multi-zone SSC modelling of 3C 279 SED: The solid curve is model fit to SED while the dashed (colored) curves shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.6, 24, 0.01, 2 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(2.7, 24, 0.3, 6.5 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-30})$ for cyan.

4.2.2 2008 SED Modelling

The 3C 279 SED presented by [26] corresponding to August to October 2008 Fermi LAT survey is also modelled in this work. In this case, as shown by Figure 29, one-zone modelling poorly fits the source SED, as lesser Compton domination is observed between optical and Fermi observations. However, it is well known that such higher optical and UV fluxes are not always produced in the jet and thermal emission from disk and BLR may contribute massively at these frequencies. The Fermi spectrum is apparently less steeper than in previous case and do not meet the expectation of one-zone model. This is because the electron cool effectively at high energies due to non-linearity of SSC cooling term [43]. Modelling the Compton peak with a single zone SSC produces lower synchrotron fluxes than observed (as consistently in previous modelling), as shown by dashed curve in Figure 29.

This inconsistency of one-zone modelling can be tackled with multi-component SSC scattering. Two zones with slightly different values of α and different par-

Figure 29. 2008 SSC modelling of 3C 279 SED: the solid curve is normal fit to data while dashed curve represents the SSC fit to Compton peak. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.1, 24, 0.05, 5 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-29})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(11, 24, 0.1, 8 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-31})$ for dashed curve.

Figure 30. 2008 multi-zone SSC modelling of 3C 279 SED: The solid curve is model fit to SED while the dashed (colored) curves show individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.7, 24, 0.008, 4 \times 10^3, 3.5 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1, 24, 0.08, 8 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-29})$ for cyan.

ticle energies contribute to observed SED. The multi-zone fit shown in Figure 30 describes the entire SED consistently. Such multi-component SSC scatterings take place within Thomson regime and contribute to observed SED. However, even with multizones, the GeV curvature cannot be adequately fit by the model. The curvature in nonlinear SSC modelling becomes prominent at higher injection parameter values $\alpha \gg 1$. Since the source is less Compton dominated ($\alpha < 1$), the model fails to fit GeV curvature and observed breaks in SED. A power law distribution might agree with the GeV curvature and high energy part of synchrotron peak.

4.2.3 Discussion

For one-zone SED fitting of both data sets, IR to optical synchrotron range and X-ray to soft gamma-ray SSC range can be self-consistently modelled, whereas the model cannot account Fermi gamma-ray emission as particles cool severely due to nonlinear SSC cooling term before GeV range. The one-zone nonlinear SSC model poorly fit the observations, as shown in Figure 27 and 29, showing that radio and IR levels severely underproduced. However, the observed SEDs of the 3C 279 well agrees with the multi-zone SSC model, similarly as in case of 3C 454.3. In this case gamma-rays can be produced by same population responsible for optical spectra while the radio-IR and soft X-ray emission can be produced from an older or cooler component with a lower electron density.

The one-zone ZS modelling of 3C 279 is in agreement many other SSC models, like [40] which fit the 2006 SED including MAGIC VHE gamma-ray data [67], and implies that one-zone SSC modelling of entire SED of the source is highly problematic and multi-zone leptonic model with external photons from BLR can explain the gamma-rays. However, their SSC code is able to produce the X-rays and gamma-rays (Figure 31) with lower optical synchrotron emission as in ZS one-zone SSC modelling. Such SSC fitting is possible using ZS model, as shown by Figure 29.

Figure 31. Spectral fits to SED of 3C 279 on 2006 February 23: The solid (red) line represents the EC model, while dashed (red) line is SSC fit produced with parameters $\gamma_1 = 10^4$, $\gamma_2 = 10^6$, $q = 2.3$ and $B = 0.2G$; (dot-dashed (maroon)) fit with the hadronic synchrotron-proton blazar model with internal (synchrotron) photons only as targets for $p\gamma$ pion production, and (long-dashed (maroon)) with synchrotron and BLR photons as targets for $p\gamma$ pion production. [40]

Another modelling effort [68] fails to produce VHE gamma emission consistently with SSC model assuming broken power law but explains the VHE emission with EC by the dusty torus IR radiation.

It has been suggested by [69] that even prior to MAGIC observations, the less energetic GeV gamma emission preferably needs an external component. This concludes that SSC modelling of gamma-rays in steady states of 3C 279 is highly difficult. Both [40] and [68] suggest the external Compton scattering must be in Thomson regime as Klein-Nishina scattering of external photons would lead to steeper VHE emission than observed. This is consistent in my results. The SED shape of 3C 279 is similar to 3C 454.3 and the parameters used satisfy the condition $K \ll 1$, implying that the source SED can only be modelled within Thomson regime.

I stress that SSC cooling can produce the gamma-ray emission consistently without the need of any external seed radiation from BLR, if multiple SSC emitting

Figure 32. Fit of ten lightcurves of 3C 279 in the optical-to-radio domain with a series of self similar synchrotron model outbursts following the spectral evolution shown in Figure 33. The contribution of individual outbursts is shown with different colors and vertical lines at the top show the times of the available SEDs. [70]

distributions with different particle densities and energies are taken into consideration. It has been suggested by [70] that multiple SSC components arise due to shock wave traveling down the jet which contribute to observed SED. The radio to optical light curves are fitted by [70] assuming individual flares as shock waves, as shown in Figure 32. The contribution of these individual synchrotron shocks to SSC spectra is shown in Figure 33. The ZS multi-zone modelling of 3C 279 sufficiently reproduces the SED assuming two synchrotron emitting zones only.

The SEDs of 3C 279, corresponding to various epochs from 1991 to 2001, have been modelled by [69] by including SSC, external radiation seed photons and including to $\gamma - \gamma$ pair production and found that variability in 3C 279 arises due to

Figure 33. Spectral decomposition of mid 1996 SED of 3C 279 derived by fitting it selfconsistently together with all the optical-to-radio lightcurves (see Figure 32). The emission from the different model outbursts, corresponding to a succession of different shock waves in the jet, is shown with the same colors as in Figure 32. The grey data points refer to historical data. [70]

changes in bulk Lorentz factor and spectral shape of electron distribution. The 1991 June flare SED fit by [69] is shown in Figure 34. The parameters used for curve fitting are electron energy limits $\gamma_1 = 350$ and $\gamma_2 = 100 \times 10^3$, electron spectral index $p = 1.90$ and bulk Lorentz factor $\gamma_{jet} = 14$ [69]. In ZS nonlinear SSC model, the SED variations can be produced by varying Lorentz factor γ_0 and Compton dominance is set by adjusting ordering parameter α .

The flare SED of a source can be speculated to arise by a single mono-energetic particle distribution in simplistic cases and nonlinear SSC models might be helpful in explaining such flares. This means that the flares can be triggered purely by injection of fresh particles into a compact region, leading to higher α . With the same ZS model, [43] modelled the powerful 2009 February outburst, as reported

Figure 34. 1991 June model SED for 3C279. Filled triangle with error bars: single measurement (or upper limit); vertical bar with no triangle: range of two or more measurements, including errors. Short-dashed line (10^{15} Hz): thermal emission from the accretion disk; short-dashed line (10^{21} Hz): disk emission Comptonized in the jet; long-dashed line: synchrotron radiation from the jet; dotted line: synchrotron self-Compton radiation from the jet; dot-dashed line: BLR emission Comptonized in the jet. [69]

Figure 35. Nonlinear SSC modelling of 2009 outburst of 3C 279. [43]

by [71], perfectly as shown in Figure 35. The high gamma-ray flux makes the source significantly Compton dominated. Since the source seems to be less Compton dominated in case of 3C 279 SEDs presented here, the one-zone model fails to fit the gamma-ray.

4.3 FSRQ Sample

In this section, the one-zone and multi-zone SED modelling fits of the rest of FSRQs sample is presented. This sample consists of Planck, Swift and Fermi bright FSRQs presented in [28]. Doppler factors for the sample are strictly based on [53]. Only simultaneously observed quasars having large Compton dominance are selected in order to test the one-zone nonlinear SSC model. The only source with less Compton dominated is 3C 273. The observed Compton dominance is not always a good idea to estimate the modelling parameters of a source, and can be sometimes misleading. It has been found that X-ray emission in 3C 273 is not purely due to SSC but many other emission mechanism [72], whereas thermal emission from dust partly contributes at IR frequencies [73]. These excesses at certain frequencies pose serious challenges to nonthermal modelling.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of 3C 273: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (1.4, 17, 0.6, 4.5 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-28})$.

(b) Multi-zone SSC modelling of 3C 273: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.9, 17, 0.7, 8 \times 10^2, 4 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (1, 17, 0.7, 5 \times 10^3, 1.5 \times 10^{-28})$ for cyan.

Figure 36. Nonlinear SSC modelling of 3C 273.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of 3C 345: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (2.5, 7.8, 2.5, 2.5 \times 10^3, 6 \times 10^{-29})$.

(b) One zone SSC modelling of 4C 11.69: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (2.5, 15.6, 0.7, 3.5 \times 10^3, 5 \times 10^{-30})$.

Figure 37. One zone Nonlinear SSC modelling of 3C345 and 4C 11.69.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of 4C 28.07: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(3.5, 16.1, 0.8, 4 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-30})$.

(b) One zone SSC modelling of 4C 29.45: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(3.5, 28.5, 0.8, 3.5 \times 10^3, 3 \times 10^{-31})$.

Figure 38. One zone Nonlinear SSC modelling of 4C 28.07 and 4C 29.45.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of 4C 38.41: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (3, 21.5, 0.1, 7 \times 10^3, 4 \times 10^{-30})$.

(b) One zone SSC modelling of NRAO 512: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (5, 19, 0.5, 6 \times 10^3, 7 \times 10^{-31})$.

Figure 39. One zone Nonlinear SSC modelling of 4C 38.41 and NRAO.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of S4 0133+47: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (2, 10, 1.5, 2.5 \times 10^3, 3 \times 10^{-29})$.

(b) One zone SSC modelling of PKS 1502+106: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (3.5, 12, 0.8, 6 \times 10^3, 7 \times 10^{-30})$.

Figure 40. One zone Nonlinear SSC modelling of S4 0133+47 and PKS 1502+106.

Figure 41. One zone SSC modelling of PKS 2227-08. The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(3.5, 15.9, 0.5, 4 \times 10^3, 3 \times 10^{-30})$.

4.4 BL Lacertae

BL Lacertae or BL Lac (2200+420) at a redshift of 0.0686 is a prototype object for BL Lac class of AGNs. It is a low peak AGN representing and classified as an LBL. According to new classification scheme based solely on location of synchrotron frequency [26], it is a classified ISP object. The BL Lacertae is a unique source as it manifests the quasars type high (10^{-41} erg s $^{-1}$) optical-UV thermal BLR line emission [74]. The source has been extensively studied and modelled in last two decades [75–78].

I model the simultaneous Planck, Swift and Fermi observations December 2009 [28] and nearly simultaneous data for Fermi observations in 2008 [26]. The SED fits for these epochs are shown in Figure 43 and 44 respectively. It is clear from the multifrequency light curves in Figure 42 that the source is overall in high state in December 2009 as compared to August-September 2008. The source shows very high optical states, especially in 2008 SED. However such higher optical-UV fluxes may not be nonthermal synchrotron radiation as BL Lac is known to include high thermal content from accretion disk, as described by [78] and [79]. Clearly one-zone

Figure 42. Multifrequency light curve for BL Lac from April 2008 to April 2010 . From top to bottom: green (Metsähovi radio observatory 37 GHz), red (Tuorla 1m optical telescope R band), blue (Swift XRT 2 – 10 keV) and pink (Fermi LAT).

Figure 43. 2009 one-zone SSC modelling of BL Lac SED: the solid curve is normal fit to data while dashed curve represents the SSC fit to Compton peak. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.7, 7.3, 0.15, 1 \times 10^4, 1 \times 10^{-26})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(4, 7.3, 0.6, 9 \times 10^3, 8 \times 10^{-29})$ for dashed curve.

ZS model fails to fit entire SED of BL Lac, especially X-rays and soft gamma-rays. However, it models the Fermi gamma-rays self-consistently with radio to optical-UV synchrotron spectrum. The source is synchrotron peak dominated as optical flux is at least equal (in 2009) or larger (in 2008) than Fermi gamma-ray flux.

Since BL Lac is an IBL, its X-ray regime belongs to transition region between synchrotron and IC components, as shown in [78] and [80]. In case of 2009 SED of the source, the XMM Newton observatory X-ray data is extracted from ASI data archive. The Swift shows decline while XMM shows rising trend along keV X-ray band, as shown in Figure 43. Both X-ray data are much flatter which proves that X-rays arise from a transition region between synchrotron and IC cooling. The steepness of the Swift UVOT data also suggests that the X-ray emission must partly arise due to synchrotron mechanism, as discussed in detail by [78]. The one-zone model fails to produce any X-rays either via synchrotron or SSC. The modelling of optical to soft X-rays synchrotron would need much higher Doppler factor and magnetic field and would poor fit to Fermi GeV data. Such parameters are not in

Figure 44. 2008 one-zone SSC modelling of BL Lac SED: the solid curve is normal fit to data while dashed curve represents the SSC fit to Compton peak. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.23, 7.3, 0.2, 1 \times 10^4, 2 \times 10^{-25})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(6, 7.3, 0.5, 1 \times 10^4, 1 \times 10^{-29})$ for dashed curve.

agreement with other models. This makes modelling of X-rays via synchrotron in one-zone model very problematic.

The 2008 SED of BL Lac has been modelled successfully by [80] with both one-zone and multi-zone SSC model but favors two zone model, as the one-zone modelling does not yield adequate fit to data. Their SSC modelling of 2008 SED is shown in Figure 46, where the radio and X-ray emission arise from a dilute region with mild parameters. In their two zone modelling, the active zones contribute to X-ray emission via both synchrotron and SSC mechanisms. The multifrequency variability pattern of the source does not show clear correlation, as shown by two years light curve (from April 2008 to April 2010) in Figure 42.

BL Lacertae is highly variable in X-rays but the Fermi gamma-rays do not show any major variability in the light curve, except a small event in April 2009. Such lack of correlation suggests that the bulk emission may not arise in same radiation blob. ZS multi-zone modelling produces reasonable fits to source SEDs, as shown in Figure 45(a) and Figure 45(b). For 2008 SED modelling, as shown in Figure

(a) 2009 multi-zone SSC modelling of BL Lac SED: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.7, 7.3, 0.7, 9 \times 10^2, 4 \times 10^{-28})$ for red, $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.7, 7.3, 0.8, 3 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-27})$ for cyan and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.7, 7.3, 0.7, 7 \times 10^3, 6 \times 10^{-27})$ for green.

(b) 2008 multi-zone SSC modelling of BL Lac SED: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.3, 7.3, 1, 2.5 \times 10^3, 1.5 \times 10^{-26})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.3, 18.0, 2, 5 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-27})$ for cyan.

Figure 45. Multizone SSC modelling of BL Lac

Figure 46. 2008 simultaneous SED of BL Lac with archival and historical data. In *Upper panel*, solid black curve shows one-zone SSC fit to simultaneous data with parameters $D = 26$, $R = 5.3 \times 10^{15}$, $B = 0.33$, $\gamma_{min} = 600$, $\gamma_{brk} = 1.4 \times 10^3$ and $\gamma_{max} = 10^6$. In *Lower panel*, the black solid curve shows overall SSC to simultaneous data while black dotted and dashed dotted curves show high energy and low energy SSC components with parameters $D_1 = 10$, $R_1 = 9 \times 10^{15}$, $B_1 = 0.45$ and $D_2 = 6.5$, $R_2 = 1.6 \times 10^{17}$, $B_2 = 0.02$, respectively. [80].

45(b), the X-rays cannot be produced either via synchrotron or SSC due to very optical state, while in case of 2009 SED the multi-component SSC model with three zones gives good fit to observations producing X-rays via SSC only. Three zones in 2009 SED modelling take same values of injection parameter, Doppler factor and magnetic field. The only parameter that demands a change is the electron Lorentz factor γ_0 .

In both single and multi-zone cases, the source can only be modelled within Thomson limit as Klein-Nishina energies, producing much lower levels, do not seem necessary to fit the Fermi gamma-rays. The injection parameter α is less than unity, suggesting that source is not Compton dominated. This implies that LBLs like BL Lac can only be modelled with multi-zone SSC model. The SED of BL Lac reveals that such sources need complex models, other than standard SSC mechanism. External models [80] and hadronic models [81] have been successfully used to model the

SED of BL Lac. The nonlinear self-consistent approach with mono-energetic electron injection may seem oversimplified and cannot plausibly model the low energy BL Lacs like BL Lac itself. The steady state SSC models with power law electron distribution might be more suitable for the source.

4.5 PKS 2155-304

The BL Lac object PKS 2155-304 at a redshift of 0.166 is the most widely studied blazar at TeV gamma-ray energies. Being the brightest X-ray selected BL Lac object [82], it was confirmed a TeV source by H.E.S.S collaboration in 2003 [83]. PKS 2155-304 is a classified HBL and observed extensively at TeV gamma-rays energies by H.E.S.S [84] and [6].

The modelling of multiwavelength data in this work corresponds to 2008 first Fermi gamma-ray observations [26]. Figure 47 shows that the entire SED can be reproduced with one SSC zone only, however the GeV Fermi gamma-rays are underproduced. Both nonlinear cooling cases with $\alpha \ll 1$ and $\alpha \gg 1$ can fit the SED assuming lower Fermi LAT flux. The nonlinear modelling with $\alpha \gg 1$ produces better fit to the X-ray tail of the synchrotron peak. The model produces a sharp cutoff in TeV. Such a sharp break is a consequence of Klein-Nishina scattering cross section. The Fermi gamma-ray spectra shows little curvature while ZS model assumes very steep GeV spectra and fits poorly to the data. This inability to produce the GeV curvature arises due to mono-energetic assumption in the model. Increasing α values cannot fit the GeV spectra. A power law or some complex distribution would produce broader SSC peak and give a more adequate fit to the observed gamma-ray spectra. However, due to lack of TeV data, the entire IC peak cannot estimated.

The value of Doppler factor $\delta = 32$ is used in modelling [85]. This value closely matches the historical literature values. The HBL source PKS 2155-304 obviously takes higher values of γ_0 and injection parameter α with lesser magnetic field than

Figure 47. 2008 SSC modelling of PKS 2155-304 SED: the solid curve is main model fit to data while dashed curve represents an alternate fit. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(4, 32.0, 0.05, 4 \times 10^5, 2 \times 10^{-27})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.9, 32.0, 0.4, 5 \times 10^4, 1.5 \times 10^{-27})$ for dashed curve.

FSRQs, which are in agreement with many other SSC models. The dashed curve in Figure 47 demands lower electron Lorentz factor but very magnetic field of several Gauss and much higher Doppler factor. Such higher magnetic field values may be unrealistic, proving that the initial linear cooling case ($\alpha \ll 1$) is not suitable to model PKS 2155-304 SED.

My modelling results can be compared to [85] which describes the simultaneous multifrequency August-September 2008 two week data complimented by H.E.S.S observations. The multifrequency light curve is shown in Figure 48. There is reasonable correlation from optical to Fermi gamma-rays while the VHE gamma-rays do not show any observable correlation. The lack of tight correlation from optical to X-ray and X-rays to VHE gamma-rays poses a serious challenge to SSC modelling of the source in general.

The SSC model fit produced by [85] is shown in Figure 49. The dotted spectrum in this model SED shows that without power law electron distribution the whole SED cannot be explained. In ZS modelling, mono-energetic electrons produce the entire

Figure 48. PKS 2155-304 multiwavelength light curve between 25 August 2008 and 6 September 2008. From top to bottom: HESS, Fermi, RXTE/Swift, and ATOM. The Fermi and RXTE/Swift panels also show the spectral index measurements (red) for each night. Vertical bars show statistical errors only. Horizontal bars represent the integration time and are apparent only for the RXTE and Fermi data. The ATOM bands are B (blue circles), V (green squares), and R (red squares). [85]

Figure 49. SED of PKS 2155-304. The red butterfly is the Fermi spectrum restricted to the MJD 54704-54715 period, while the black butterfly covers MJD 54682-54743. The gray points are archival NED archival data, and the two gray butterflies are EGRET measurements. The solid line is a one-zone SSC model. The dashed and the dot-dashed lines are the same model without electrons above γ_1 and γ_2 , respectively. [85]

synchrotron peak completely but poorly fit to the GeV gamma-rays. The higher α produces broken power laws even with the simplest mono-energetic injection case. This suggest that nonlinear SSC cooling with more realistic electron distribution may be considered in TeV BL Lacs like PKS 2155-304.

Many SSC models adequately produce the SED fits of PKS 2155-304 assuming more realistic electron spectra. [86] models the 2008 SED, as shown in Figure 50, by the evolution of mono-energetic electron injected ($\gamma_0 = 910$) into acceleration zone under the influence of Fermi acceleration processes. For complete set of model parameters used in Figure 50, see Table 1 in [86]. I conclude that a one-zone nonlinear SSC modelling with mono-energetic electron energy spectrum is problematic and a more realistic electron distributions must be used.

Figure 50. SSC modelling of PKS 2155-304 of simultaneous August-September 2008 data (red). The 2003 H.E.S.S data (blue circles) is also shown, proving the lowstate. Produced by [86]

4.6 Mrk 501

Mrk 501 is amongst the nearest HBLs at a redshift of 0.034. It is a first generation observed extragalactic TeV BL Lac source and has been observed intensively over the last two decades. It was discovered to be a TeV bright source by Whipple in 1996 [87] and went a powerful VHE outburst being 10 times brighter than Crab Nebula in 1997 April [88]. Afterwards, the source has been consistently studied by multifrequency observations, particularly in high energy range [89, 90]. Almost a decade later after its discovery in VHE gamma-rays, Mrk 501 experienced an extreme and highly variable flare in 2005 [91].

4.6.1 SED Modelling

The SED of Mrk 501, described by [28], includes Planck through Fermi data corresponding to March 2010 simultaneous data. Another dataset with quasi-simultaneous data taken between 2008 and 2009 [26] is also modelled in order to verify the modelling results. Both data sets are complemented by 2009 March MAGIC TeV data

Figure 51. 2010 one-zone SSC modelling of Mrk 501: the solid curve is main model fit to data while dashed curve represents an alternate fit. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(10, 12.0, 0.4, 6 \times 10^5, 1.5 \times 10^{-26})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.8, 40.0, 0.7, 3.5 \times 10^4, 1 \times 10^{-28})$ for dashed curve.

extracted from the ASI data center. This data being non-simultaneous is just used to constrain the SED, however, the actual TeV state of the source may be far different.

The multifrequency light curve from optical to Fermi gamma-rays for the source is shown in Figure 53. The radio light ray curve shows that Mrk 501 is a weak radio source with historical flux $F_{37GHz} < 1.5$ Jy, whereas the source is highly variable in Fermi gamma-rays, optical and X-rays. Due to such strange behaviour of the source, it is difficult to see any correlation just by visual inspection. The 2010 and 2008 SED modelling of the source is shown in Figure 51 and Figure 52 respectively. There are two modelling fits for each SED including the cases with $\alpha \gg 1$ and $\alpha \ll 1$ which are shown by solid and dashed curves respectively.

The one-zone modelling accounts for radio to X-ray synchrotron emission but cannot satisfactorily match the curvature of synchrotron peak and underproduces the GeV gamma-rays. Nonlinear modelling produces a sharp cutoff in TeV which appears due to nonlinear SSC mechanism in Klein-Nishina effects [43]. This poor

Figure 52. 2008 one-zone SSC modelling of Mrk 501: the solid curve is main model fit to data while dashed curve represents an alternate fit. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(12, 12.0, 0.1, 9 \times 10^5, 1 \times 10^{-26})$ for solid curve and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.7, 40.0, 0.2, 4 \times 10^4, 9 \times 10^{-29})$ for dashed curve.

fitting of X-rays and gamma-rays is also reported by simplest SSC model [110]. Due to very sharp cutoff just after SSC peak, the model poorly fit the TeV data as shown in Figure 51. This implies that nonlinear cooling mechanism may not be responsible for the TeV emission.

In case of $\alpha \ll 1$, the model fails to produce X-rays at all and the blob cools in low energy part of Swift X-rays as depicted by dashed curve in Figure 51 and Figure 52. These dashed fits assume higher values of either magnetic field or Doppler factor and mild particle energies (order of 10^4). The poor fitting to X-rays and GeV gamma-rays, in case of $\alpha \ll 1$, shows that mono-energetic electron distribution cannot explain the SED of Mrk 501 if cooling is initially linear. With $\alpha \gg 1$ and high particle energies (γ_0 being order of 10^5), the one-zone model faily fits the entire synchrotron peak by producing broken power law type spectra due to activation of nonlinear SSC cooling initially, as shown by solid curves in Figure 51 and 52. Interestingly, the curvature becomes more obvious and clear with increasing α . Hence the higher values of α and γ_0 produce convincing fits to Mrk 501 SED.

Figure 53. Multifrequency light curve for Mrk 501 from April 2008 to April 2010 . From top to bottom: green (Metsähovi radio observatory 37 GHz), red (Tuorla 1m optical telescope R band), blue (Swift XRT 2 – 10 keV) and pink (Fermi LAT GeV).

Figure 54. 2010 multi-zone SSC modelling of Mrk 501 SED: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.4, 15.0, 0.2, 2 \times 10^4, 4 \times 10^{-24})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (4.5, 40.0, 1.0, 2.2 \times 10^5, 7 \times 10^{-29})$ for cyan.

The model nicely fits GeV data but underproduces TeV spectra.

The multi-zone modelling of Mrk 501 can explain the TeV emission through SSC, as shown in Figure 54. In this case, the VHE gamma-rays and TeV emission arise from a compact source with synchrotron peak at X-rays. This corresponds to a dense knot at $\alpha = 4.5$ at high energy $\gamma_0 = 2.2 \times 10^5$ with high Doppler factor $D \geq 40$. The Fermi gamma-rays emerge from a dilute $\alpha \leq 1$ and cooler blob with less Doppler factor $D = 15$. In such modelling, the different Doppler factors may correspond to two physically separated emission zones. Since there is not enough variability correlation at low and high energy bands of Mrk 501, the lower and higher energy emission may be appear from different blobs, justifying my modelling.

4.6.2 Discussion

Doppler factor $\delta = 12$ is used in modelling and match the literature values [93,94]. Using $\delta = 12$, I get almost similar magnetic field values while particle energy well in between γ_{min} and γ_{max} , presented in their modelling. [93] models the time averaged

Figure 55. SSC modelling of Mrk 501 between 1997 April and 1999 June. For 1997 April, the model parameters used are $\delta = 10$, $b = 0.32$, $\gamma_{brk} = 7 \times 10^5$, $n_1 = 1.55$ and $n_2 = 3$. [95]

SED with SSC with broken power law electron distribution using magnetic field $b = 0.015$ G, doppler factor $\delta = 12$ with a power law particle spectra with minimum and maximum energies of $\gamma_{min} = 600$ and $\gamma_{max} = 1.5 \times 10^7$. For complete list of parameters, refer to Table 2 in the original paper. The historical SEDs of the source for different epochs between 1997 and 1999 have been modelled by [95] which uses broken power law electron distribution. Their break energy closely matches the mono-energetic particle energy used in my modelling with similar other parameters as well. This shows that ZS model is very effective in HBLs like Mrk 501, in which the observed breaks in the spectra naturally occur.

It has been suggested by [96] that a nonlinear correlation between X-rays and VHE gamma-ray fluxes and supports full Klein-Nishina cross section when computing SSC spectra. When Klein-Nishina parameter $K \gg 1$ in ZS modelling, much higher injection parameter is needed to produces the SSC peak due to Klein-Nishina decrease of cross-section. The lower and higher state SED modelling of Mrk 501

by [95] is shown in Figure 55, and the complete set of modelling parameters are described in Table 5 of original publication. Both [95] and [97] propose that spectral variations and higher and lower states of the source can be reproduced by only changing the electron Lorentz factor. However the ZS modelling results consistently in agreement with [98] claiming that higher and lower state modelling demand a change in other parameters like magnetic field, Doppler factor and size of the source.

It has been observed while modelling that shifting from $\alpha \ll 1$ to $\alpha \gg 1$, higher values of α and γ_0 and lower magnetic field b are needed. This shows that a higher energy of electrons should be complemented with a higher density and thus higher injection. In this way, the decrease in SSC cross section in Klein-Nishina regime can be compensated by adding more electrons into jet. The one-zone modelling in Thomson regime ($K \ll 1$) unrealistically needs much higher values of Doppler factor and magnetic field strength of several Gauss. Thus the ZS model can only be used to model HBLs like Mrk 501 when Klein-Nishina effects on electron distribution are considered.

4.7 Mrk 421

Mrk 421 is one of the brightest extragalactic HBL at a redshift of 0.031. It was the the first extragalactic object detected at VHE gamma-rays ($E > 500$ GeV) [99]. Mrk 421 is a variable gamma-ray source [100] with significant SED variations observed in lower and higher states [101]. Many multifrequency campaigns were organized in last decade to study the SED and spectral variability of the source, [92, 102, 103].

4.7.1 SED Modelling

The November 2009 SED of the source, with simultaneous Planck, Swift XRT and Fermi observations, is reported by [28] while no UVOT observations are available. In case of quasi simultaneous August-October 2008 [26], the MAGIC TeV data is

extracted from ASI data center and included in the SED. The optical to gamma-ray light curves from April 2008 to April 2010 is shown in Figure 56. The nonlinear modelling fits to these SEDs is given in Figure 57 and 58 respectively. The 2009 SED shown in Figure 57 represents higher state as compared to relatively quiet 2008 state, which shown in Figure 58.

Mrk 421 SED efficiently agrees with expectations of ZS model. Both 2008 and 2009 states of the source are adequately modelled with one-zone SSC model without need of any multizones. In 2009, the source is in higher X-rays state and gamma-ray state and the gamma-ray spectra are harder than in 2008. Such harder GeV spectra meet nicely to one-zone model fit. The higher values of injection parameter α produce broken power law type spectra introducing breaks in synchrotron peak and TeV gamma-rays. Due to very sharp break in VHE gamma-rays, the model fits poorly to TeV spectra. The breaks and curvature in X-rays get more prominent at higher α and γ_0 as in case of Mrk 501. Since very steep cooling is not observed in Mrk 421, moderate values are used.

(a) Tuorla optical 1m telescope light curve

(b) Swift X-rays light curve

(c) Fermi light curve

Figure 56. Multifrequency light curve for Mrk 421 from April 2008 to April 2010 . From top to bottom: red (Tuorla 1m optical telescope R band), blue (Swift XRT 2 – 10 keV) and pink (Fermi LAT GeV).

Figure 57. 2009 SSC modelling of Mrk 421: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(12, 21, 0.5, 6 \times 10^5, 1.5 \times 10^{-26})$.

Figure 58. 2008 SSC modelling of Mrk 421: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(9, 21, 0.6, 4 \times 10^5, 3 \times 10^{-27})$.

4.7.2 Discussion

It has been observed while modelling the source SEDs that a reduction in injection parameter α must be complemented by lower particle energies (γ_0) and very high Doppler factor ($\delta \geq 40$). Such higher Doppler factors (or even much higher than 40) are have been used in literature [92, 102]. However, the source SED can be best fit at $\delta = 21$, which is almost double the value used for Mrk 501. This value closely match to those frequently used in literature [100, 103, 104]. With $\alpha \ll 1$, the one-zone modelling of the source would take very high values of Doppler factor ($\delta \gg 50$), very high magnetic field ($B \gg 3$ Gauss) and lower particle energies ($\gamma_0 \ll 10^5$), but fails to match the observed curvature in X-rays. This implies that in Thomson regime, the nonlinear cooling term cannot fit the X-rays spectrum. This result is similar to that of Mrk 501.

Mrk 421 is a weak radio source, as shown by Metsähovi 37 GHz radio light curve from 2008 to 2011 in Figure 59. The source is historically well below than 1 Jy and fluctuates from 0.1 to 0.7 Jy. Due to less sensitivity below 1 Jy, the observed fluctuations seems to arise due to noise while the source can be assumed to be at a constant level. Mrk 421, like Mrk 501, is also highly variable source in Fermi gamma-ray band. The one-zone ZS model over-produces radio data and suggests that such low radio emission may arise from a different synchrotron emitting electron population down in the jet.

One other implication of nonlinear cooling assumes harder gamma-ray and TeV spectra than commonly observed, as discussed in case of Mrk 501. The strong TeV break obviously arises due to the Klein-Nishina effect on nonlinear SSC cooling rate, canceling the contribution of synchrotron photons emitted above the synchrotron peak to observed SSC luminosity [104]. This proposes that more complex electron distributions should be used in nonlinear cooling case. A power law or multiple power law electron distribution is employed successfully by various SSC models (as

Figure 59. Metsähovi radio observatory 37 GHz light curve of Mrk 421. The green point show observations and vertical red lines are error bars.

referred in this section), adequately fitting the SED of HBL Mrk 421 and Mrk 501. However, most of the time, such power law distributions are used just to fit the SED data without any theoretical reasoning and justification. The ZS model shows that with nonlinear SSC term, the observed breaks in the spectra can be produced even in simplest cases with mono-energetic electron energy. This indicates that observed curvature in SED may not arise by the breaks in particle distribution, but due to nonlinear SSC cooling effect which many models do not consider.

Hadronic synchrotron modelling of VHE spectra of Mrk 501 and Mrk 421 [93, 103]. For some sources, [105] suggests high energy emission due to proton synchrotron from a compact region with high magnetic field while low energy emission originates from an extended leptonic jet. This hadronic modelling may be suitable for very high energy gamma-rays, as ZS model produces a cutoff in this energy range. However the multi-zone modelling of these sources, in order to account for TeV spectra, is recommended and such modelling hints are presented in the literature, for example in [106]. This can be particularly true for the orphan TeV flares. In multi-zone modelling, the TeV spectra can be modelled with parameters corresponding to

a compact region with higher α and γ_0 .

4.8 BL Lac Sample

In this section, the one-zone and multi-zone SED modelling fits of the rest of BL Lac sample are presented. This sample consists of Planck, Swift and Fermi bright BL Lacs presented in [28]. The sample includes an IBL object ON 231 as well as an HBL object 1H 1013+498. The BL Lacs appear to be less Compton dominated than FSRQs. The cause of less Compton domination is not clear, however, it is generally attributed to less contribution to high energy IC emission due to lack of powerful BLR radiation field [30]. The Doppler factors for the sample are strictly based on [53]. In few cases where literature Doppler factors are unavailable, best fits have been used to constrain Doppler factors.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of OJ 287: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.4, 17, 0.1, 7 \times 10^3, 6 \times 10^{-28})$.

(b) Multi-zone SSC modelling of OJ 287: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.4, 17.0, 0.1, 2 \times 10^3, 2 \times 10^{-28})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.4, 17.0, 0.6, 5 \times 10^3, 4 \times 10^{-28})$ for cyan.

Figure 60. Nonlinear SSC modelling of OJ 287

(a) One zone SSC modelling of ON 231: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.6, 10, 1, 4 \times 10^3, 7 \times 10^{-28})$.

(b) Multi-zone SSC modelling of ON 231: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.6, 10, 1, 1.5 \times 10^3, 8 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm) = (0.6, 10, 1.5, 4.5 \times 10^3, 8 \times 10^{-28})$ for cyan.

Figure 61. Nonlinear SSC modelling of ON 231

(a) One zone SSC modelling of OT 081: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1, 12, 0.1, 7 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-28})$.

(b) Multi-zone SSC modelling of OT 081: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.8, 12, 0.05, 2 \times 10^3, 6 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.0, 12, 0.3, 7 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-28})$ for cyan.

Figure 62. Nonlinear SSC modelling of OT 081

(a) One zone SSC modelling of S5 1803+784: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.9, 12.2, 0.2, 5 \times 10^3, 1 \times 10^{-28})$.

(b) Multi-zone SSC modelling of S5 1803+784: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.8, 12.2, 0.2, 2 \times 10^3, 5 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(0.8, 12.2, 0.5, 6 \times 10^3, 1.5 \times 10^{-28})$ for cyan.

Figure 63. Nonlinear SSC modelling of S5 1803+784.

(a) One zone SSC modelling of PKS 0332-403: The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(2, 15, 1, 3 \times 10^3, 6 \times 10^{-30})$.

(b) Multi-zone SSC modelling of PKS 0332-403: The solid curve is model fit to SED while dashed (colored) curve shows individual components. The parameters used are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1, 15, 0.05, 3 \times 10^3, 1.3 \times 10^{-29})$ for red and $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(1.3, 15, 0.1, 1 \times 10^4, 2 \times 10^{-28})$ for cyan.

Figure 64. Nonlinear SSC modelling of PKS 0332-403.

Figure 65. Nonlinear SSC modelling of 1H 1013+498. The parameters used to fit model are $(\alpha, D, B, \gamma_0, Norm)=(10, 8, 0.15, 4 \times 10^5, 8 \times 10^{-27})$.

4.9 Parameter Correlation

I study the proportionality between the global parameters obtained by one-zone fitting of SEDs of blazar sample. This correlation is not measured statistically but just by visual inspection of the data. These source parameters used in one-zone modelling of entire sample are listed in Table 3. The source types and classification mentioned in column 2 and 3 of Table 3 are based on [28] and [29].

4.9.1 α vs γ_0

The BL Lacs (LBLs and HBLs) are apparently less Compton dominated than FSRQs and possess higher synchrotron peaks, as reported by [28]. This assumes that low peaked FSRQs have higher injection parameter and interpret their high luminosity in Blazar Sequence as a result of higher injection of electrons rather than EC. The less dominance of BL Lacs can be interpreted as a consequence of decrease of SSC cross-section at higher particle energies. Interestingly, there seems to be a significant proportionality between α and γ_0 , as shown by Figure 66. FSRQs on the average have injection parameter $\alpha > 1.5$, whereas LBLs possess values $\alpha < 1$. HBLs have

Table 3. Parameters used for one-zone modelling.

Source	Type	Class	α	D	B	γ_0	$Norm$	$\log(\nu_s)$
3C 279	FSRQ	LSP	3.7	24	1.5	2400	1.00E-030	12.90
3C 454.3	FSRQ	LSP	4	33	1	3000	3.00E-030	13.40
3C 273	FSRQ	LSP	1.4	17	0.6	4500	1.00E-028	14.10
3C 345	FSRQ	LSP	2.5	7.8	2.5	2500	6.00E-029	12.20
4C 11.69	FSRQ	LSP	2.5	15.6	0.7	3500	5.00E-030	13.20
4C 28.07	FSRQ	LSP	3.5	16.1	0.8	4000	2.00E-030	13.30
4C 29.45	FSRQ	LSP	3.3	28.5	0.8	3500	3.00E-031	13.45
4C 38.41	FSRQ	LSP	3	21.5	0.1	7000	4.00E-030	13.20
NRAO 512	FSRQ	LSP	5	19	0.5	6000	7.00E-031	13.25
S4 0133+47	FSRQ	LSP	2	10	1.5	2500	3.00E-029	13.40
PKS 1502+106	FSRQ	LSP	3.5	12	0.8	6000	7.00E-030	13.44
PKS 2227-08	FSRQ	LSP	3.5	15.9	0.5	4000	3.00E-030	13.15
PKS 2155-304	BL Lac	HSP	4	32	0.05	400000	2.00E-027	16.30
Mrk 501	BL Lac	HSP	10	12	0.4	600000	1.50E-026	16.40
Mrk 421	BL Lac	HSP	12	21	0.5	600000	1.00E-026	16.60
1H 1013+498	BL Lac	HSP	10	8	0.15	400000	8.00E-027	15.40
BL Lac	BL Lac	ISP	0.7	7.3	0.15	10000	1.00E-026	14.00
PKS 0235+164	BL Lac	LSP	4	24	0.3	4500	4.00E-031	13.20
OJ 287	BL Lac	LSP	0.4	17	0.1	7000	6.00E-028	13.26
ON 231	BL Lac	ISP	0.6	10	1	4000	7.00E-028	14.34
OT 081	BL Lac	LSP	1	12	0.1	7000	1.00E-028	13.40
S5 1803+784	BL Lac	LSP	0.9	12.2	0.2	5000	1.00E-028	13.40
PKS 0332-403	BL Lac	LSP	2	15	1	3000	6.00E-030	13.25
PKS 0426-380	BL Lac	LSP	1.5	12	0.5	5000	2.00E-029	13.28

Figure 66. Electron Lorentz factor (γ_0) vs Injection parameter (α). The red circles represent FSRQs, the green triangles LBLs and the blue triangles HBLs.

exceptionally high values $\alpha > 3$ and $\gamma_0 > 10^5$ which makes them the most compact sources. In case of HBLs, a higher α does not correspond to physical high Compton domination. These high α values are needed to compensate the decrease in SSC losses in Klein-Nishina limit. Figure 66 suggests that the higher energetic electron injection should be supported by a higher injection itself. This is obvious as higher energies affect efficiency of SSC scattering and should be supported by high density of injected electron in the jet.

4.9.2 B vs γ_0

There is an overall negative correlation observed between magnetic field B and electron Lorentz factor γ_0 , as shown by Figure 67. FSRQs take higher magnetic field ($B = 0.1 - 3$) on the average than BL Lacs ($B = 0.01 - 1$). Among BL Lacs, HBLs even require smaller magnetic field values than LBLs. Recently, the Fermi bright BL Lacs have been modelled with broken power law electron spectrum, but no correlation was observed between magnetic field and break energy γ_b [107].

Figure 67. Electron Lorentz factor (γ_0) vs magnetic field (b). The red circles represent FSRQs and the blue triangles BL Lacs.

4.9.3 γ_0 vs ν_s

There seems to be an overall positive correlation between the electron Lorentz factor γ_0 and synchrotron peak frequency ν_s and shown in Figure 68. This means that HSP sources have high electron energies. This again predicts the lower Compton dominance of HSP sources in the blazar sequence due to higher electron energies.

Figure 68. Synchrotron peak $\log(\nu_s)$ vs Lorentz factor (γ_0). The red circles represent FSRQs, the green triangles LBLs, and the blue triangles HBLs.

5 Results and Discussion

I studied SEDs of gamma-ray blazars including selected FSRQs and BL Lacs from published simultaneous observations [28] and quasi simultaneous observations [26]. I infer that a homogeneous one-zone nonlinear SSC model (ZS Model) explains the SEDs of Compton dominated blazars where inverse Compton losses dominate the SED, but fails to model the blazars where synchrotron peak dominate, especially LBLs and some FSRQs in low states.

My modelling results are in agreement with those of [28] and [26] and many other physical models which argue that one-zone SSC models cannot suffice LSP blazars. The ZS model fails to fit quiescent SEDs of FSRQs and LBLs. Recently, [107] studied modelling of BL Lac sample presented in [26] and found that SSC model can fit the observations only in case of HBLs and IBLs while LBLs cannot be modelled.

Many models and studies suggest that the gamma emission is produced when the blob crosses the BLR radiation [10]. However, according to ZS model, the gamma emission can be produced simply by increasing the injection (electron density) of electrons into jet. I argue that ZS model should be considered especially in the cases where the gamma emission is produced without the influence of BLR, as generally believed in BL Lacs. The model fully describes the spectra of flaring FSRQs with gamma-ray flux doubling (or higher orders) episodes in Thomson IC cooling regime. In low gamma states of LSP sources (LBLs and FSRQs), the multi-zone SSC modelling can explain the entire SED and doesn't require either any fancy electron distributions or external radiation components like BLR radiation and accretion disk photons to account for very high energy emission. I argue that ZS model, that includes time dependent non-equilibrium SSC cooling term, can potentially be used to investigate the spectra of such powerful flaring sources and constraining the emission parameters and conditions. Such severe SSC cooling is justified in extreme gamma flares, where a nonlinear flux correlation between low and high energy bands

exists.

This work shows the potential of mono-energetic injection against steady state models that use linear SSC relations assuming broken power law distributions, as in [107]. The models assuming power laws may produce broad synchrotron and SSC peaks but they seem to fail producing higher gamma-ray luminosity. The ZS model interpret the observed higher Compton dominance in some blazars as a result of higher order of cooling of mono-energetic particles in the jet, rather assuming external Compton (EC) process which is sometimes invoked just to fit high gamma-ray fluxes without physical reasoning. According to ZS model, the extreme gamma-ray flares (where gamma-ray flux increases by many orders) are driven by a higher particle injection into active zone.

The SED variations can be produced by varying both α and γ_0 . For $\alpha \ll 1$, the synchrotron peak follows a power law $\nu^{1/2}$ and cuts-off exponentially, while in case of $\alpha \gg 1$, the synchrotron and SSC peak follow double power law. This fact is different to linear SSC models assuming broken power law spectra, where the SED variations can be merely produced by varying upper and lower electron energy limits γ_{max} and γ_{min} and indices p_1 and p_2 . This implies that change in SED shape is related to value of injection parameter α and not only electron Lorentz factor γ_0 . A correlation between α and γ_0 has been observed in this work, suggesting that higher electron energies must be complemented by a higher injection.

5.1 FSRQs and LBLs

The inverse Compton peak in many Compton dominated sources fits nicely to observations by increasing α and γ_0 in one-zone ZS model, which means that IC emission can intrinsically arise by higher injection of relativistic electrons submitted to initial nonlinear cooling, rather than External Compton modelling which consider the contribution of soft seed photons from BLR, accretion disk or dusty torus. A slight

increase in α manifests as a sharp increase in SSC luminosity, reproducing higher Compton dominance, as seen in FSRQ sample selected in this work. High flux gamma-ray flares or an orphan gamma-ray flare can account for such high dominance of inverse Compton peak. The Nonlinear SSC modelling with $\alpha > 1$ describes the SEDs of such sources efficiently, as presented in FSRQ sample. This implies that in such powerful gamma bright sources, the cooling initially becomes nonlinear and high gamma flux emerge due to higher injection of mono-energetic particles in the jet rather than any other mechanism. However in many cases of FSRQ sample, the ZS model cools before reaching GeV Fermi gamma-ray bands and predicts much steeper spectra in this frequency range. Such very steep cooling is rarely observed. This is obviously due to fact that nonlinear cooling operates effectively on higher energy electrons. One zone SSC Model is, however, not suitable for quiescent states of FSRQs and LBLs as seen in case 3C 454.3, 3C 279 and BL Lacertae, as it fails to fit the observations self-consistently. The external modelling of quiet FSRQs (including nonlinear SSC), as formulated recently by [45], may fit the entire SEDs of such sources. However, [45] states that despite EC can fairly fit the VHE part of SED, the contribution of nonlinear SSC term is still inevitable.

In case of $\alpha < 1$, the model produces much narrower peaks and fails to fit the entire peaks in the SED. This has been demonstrated in case of low states of 3C 279 and 3C 454.3 and LBL sample. This indicates that initial linear cooling cannot be employed to model the quiescent state SEDs of sources with lower Compton dominance. In this case, a power law electron distribution shall work better. In low states, the fitting of entire SSC peak takes higher α and γ_0 produces much lower synchrotron levels from radio to UV, suggesting that nonlinear SSC mechanism may not be responsible for such SEDs. The underproduced synchrotron levels can be justified in some cases, where the observed optical-UV fluxes emerge from thermal emission of accretion disk and radio-IR emission arise due to some older electron

population. However, such scenario is not always possible, as a same electron population must be responsible for observed synchrotron and inverse Compton emission in self-consistent models and due to fact that the gamma flares usually follow the radio flares [108]. BL Lac sample is less Compton dominated as compared to FSRQs and one-zone modelling fails to model these sources. In these sources the typical injection parameter α remains $0.1 - 1$ and, thus, initial linear modelling becomes unfit for these sources.

The model assumes a strong dip observed in the GeV spectra of FSRQs and LBLs after $(\nu) > 10^{24}$, which is not observed as the GeV spectra usually are flatter than expectations of the model. For mild energies ($10^3 \geq \gamma_0 \leq 10^4$) and magnetic field strength ($0.1 - 5$ Gauss), such GeV cutoff cannot be produced by ZS Model and the particles cool before reproducing the observed curvature. This is particularly true for low gamma states. This is because when Klein-Nishina parameter K is less than unity (Thomson limit), the SSC cooling term (at lower values of alpha $\alpha \ll 1$) cannot produce broken power law type spectra as discussed in Section 3.1 and, therefore, the model fails to meet the GeV curvature. Thus a high energy zone must be added to account for gamma-ray spectra. However, the gamma-ray spectra are steeper in flaring sources and well agree the expectations of model.

To overcome the difficulties associated with one-zone modelling of quiescent FSRQs and LBLs, the multi-zone SSC is also employed to account for entire observed SED of FSRQs and LBLs. Multiple SSC modelling is preferable in low states and provides a good alternative to power law or broken power laws. In this scenario, multiple particle distributions with different particle energies seem to account for overall SED. In many cases two zone SSC model suffice BL Lac sources presented in the sample and low state FSRQs such as BL Lac, OJ 287, 3C 454.3, 3C 279, etc. The high energy emission (from IR-to-optical and MeV-to-GeV) arises from the main jet while low energies (radio-to-IR and keV-to-MeV) arise in a dilute or less active re-

gion. The gamma-rays in many BL Lacs are efficiently reproduced by the scattering of IR-optical synchrotron photons. In practice, many SSC modelling efforts leave out radio to IR synchrotron fluxes without solid justifications. This is not justified at least in the cases where radio flares provide significant contribution to SSC. The ZS multi-zone model accounts for this low energy synchrotron content consistently. In multiple SSC scattering, the electrons in active zone not only scatter the local synchrotron photon but the photons from the other region as well. The multi-zone modelling challenges the EC models that generally employ photon sources external to jet in order to meet the observations. The multi-zone SSC modelling is accepted especially in those cases there a strong multifrequency variability patterns correlation is observed. In IBLs, like BL Lac and ON 231, the X-rays cannot be modelled consistently via either synchrotron or SSC. This is, however, understandable as the X-ray emission in such sources arise from a transition region between synchrotron and SSC processes, as discussed in case of BL Lacertae.

5.2 HBLs

The one-zone SSC model meets well with observed SEDs of HSP BL Lacs (HBLs). This is strongly in agreement with many previous SSC models like [109] that uses a power law or a broken power law electron distributions and steady state cooling relations.

In TeV BL Lacs like PKS 2155-304, Mrk 421 and Mrk 501, higher electron energies and need higher injection of electrons are required to fit the source SEDs, as shown by Figure 66. The one-zone SSC suffice the HBLs. The curvature to synchrotron peak (at X-rays) can be matched using higher values of injection parameter $\alpha \gg 1$ and electrons energies corresponding to Klein-Nishina regime. This is expected as [43] suggests that second power law after the synchrotron peak becomes broader while increasing α . This curvature is produced purely as a consequence of

nonlinear cooling term without inducing any breaks in electron spectrum. The HBLs need higher particle energies than FSRQs and LBLs to produce the TeV or High energy spectra. At higher electron energies, the Thomson cross-section is replaced by Klein-Nishina cross-section and ZS model produces sharp break in VHE gamma in TeV regime, as seen in Mrk 501 and Mrk 421. Such sharp cooling is not always observed in TeV SEDs of BL Lacs. The poor fitting to TeV data is justified as TeV rays can arise due to an orphan flare and provide motivation for multi-component SSC modelling to match the SED [110]. The modelling of HBL source takes much higher electron energy ($\gamma_0 \geq 10^5$) and lower magnetic field ($b = 0.01 - 1$ Gauss) than LSP objects. These parameter values are typical of Klein-Nishina limit ($K \gg 1$). My modelling results and parameter values for HBLs are in agreement with [38] and [109].

The model also assumes a harder Fermi GeV gamma-rays, however such harder Fermi spectra are not always observed. Especially the 27 months integrated Fermi data presented in [28] is flatter than simultaneous data, so one-zone ZS model fails to meet such time integrated gamma-ray data in both LSP and HSP objects. The mononenergetic assumption in ZS model seem to cause problems for modelling of VHE gamma-rays. Since the spectra after synchrotron and SSC peak is affected by the choice of electron distribution [43], a more complex electron distribution would produce better fits to TeV SED of HSPs/HBLs.

The multi-frequency correlation studies pose challenges to the one-zone SSC modelling of HBLs. Generally the VHE gamma-rays do not correlate with optical to X-rays. This fact suggest that the entire emission may not be arising from a same location and favors multi-zone modelling. In multi-zone modelling, the VHE gamma-ray emission arises due to compact jet which is described as an inner core in Spine-sheath jet models. The less energetic spectra arise from a dilute region with mild parameters. Such multi-zone modelling is shown in case of Mrk 501 in Section

4. This shows that the TeV spectra of HBLs can still be modelled in nonlinear SSC framework.

5.3 Summary and Conclusion

I have modelled the radio to gamma-rays bright blazar sample, taken from [28], with a nonlinear SSC model [43]. I find that Compton dominated sources can be fairly modelled using nonlinear SSC cooling term, contrary to steady state SSC models that often fail to explain the high IC luminosity of flaring sources. This implies that the higher Compton domination in compact flaring blazars is set by a higher injection of mono-energetic particles into the jet. Usually, in case of FSRQs, the higher Compton domination in blazar sequence is explained due to enhancement of radiation field external to jet and EC modelling is employed [32] to account for very high gamma-ray fluxes. I argue that the higher gamma-ray luminosity, and thus higher Compton domination, in flaring sources is linked to an increase in density of electrons injected into radiation blob. In this way, the interpretation for standard blazar sequence [32] can be questioned.

The choice of shape of electron spectrum may be important in nonlinear modelling. While the one-zone ZS model with mono-energetic electron distribution suffice the high compton dominated FSRQs, it fails to match the SEDs of less dominated or quiescent LSP FSRQs and LBLs. A more complex electron distribution should be used in order to test the potential of nonlinear SSC cooling term. However, a multi-component SSC can model the low state sources. Like steady state SSC models, a one-zone ZS model fairly fits the SEDs of HSP sources (HBLs). This suggests that the broader synchrotron peak and breaks in observed SEDs of these sources can be explained by nonlinear cooling effect. I conclude that nonlinear SSC model with different electron spectra can be efficiently used to model the nonthermal flaring blazars.

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